

SafeHabitus

Deliverable D3.3

Farm Health and Safety in the EU: Needs, Challenges and Opportunities

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Acronyms

ASIF - Agricultural Social Insurance Fund

EU – European Union

CAP – Common Agricultural Policy

CATPCA / PCA -Categorical Principal Component Analysis

CoP – Community of Practice

DOI – Diffusion of Innovation

DUERP – Occupational Risk Assessment Document

HOC – Hierarchy of Control

MSDs – Musculoskeletal Disorders

JSKS - Agricultural Advisory Service

KGZS - Chamber of Agriculture and Forestry of Slovenia

LAAS - Lithuanian Agricultural Advisory Service

NGO – Non-Governmental Organisation

OSH – Occupational Safety and Health

PPE – Personal Protective Equipment

PTO – Power Take-off

SEM – Socioecological Model

SVLFG – Sozialversicherung für Landwirtschaft, Forsten und Gartenbau

TN – Technical Note

TSS - Technical Supervisory Service

WCSS - Within-Cluster Sum of Squares

Executive Summary

Context and Rationale

Agriculture remains one of the most hazardous occupations in the European Union. Eurostat data indicate an average annual work-related injury rate of 1,653 per 100,000 agricultural workers and a fatality rate of 4.1 per 100,000. Recent SafeHabitus research suggests these official figures substantially underestimate the true burden, with fatal injury rates potentially 70% higher when accounting for self-employed farmers excluded from EU reporting systems. Despite decades of prevention efforts, injury and fatality rates have remained persistently high, indicating that current approaches—while valuable—are insufficient to address the complexity of agricultural safety challenges.

This deliverable addresses a fundamental gap in the evidence base for European farm safety policy: the need to understand both what safety priorities experts and stakeholders identify as most pressing, and how farmers themselves prefer to engage with safety information and services. By synthesising these two perspectives across 11 EU Member States, this research provides evidence for policy development at a critical point in time—as the Post-2027 Common Agricultural Policy framework enters legislative negotiation whilst grappling with the challenges of sustaining the attractiveness of farming.

Scope and Approach

This deliverable reports findings from two complementary studies conducted across Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Ireland, Lithuania, Poland, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, and Spain. Both studies employed the SafeHabitus Community of Practice (CoP) model, bringing together researchers, advisors, farmers, and stakeholders in each country to ensure findings are grounded in local contexts while enabling cross-national synthesis.

Study 1 (Priority Needs Register) systematically captured expert and stakeholder knowledge through structured consultation with CoPs in all 11 countries leading to the development of the SafeHabitus Needs Register. This process identified 229 specific safety and health hazards, issues, challenges, and needs, organised by hazard category and responsible actor group. Critically, the analysis revealed underpinning constructs—systemic social, cultural, and economic factors—that shape safety outcomes beyond immediate hazards.

Study 2 (Survey and Cluster Analysis) surveyed 1,078 farmers, farmworkers, family members, and agricultural students to identify safety priorities and engagement preferences. The survey instrument combined an expanded Hierarchy of Controls framework with the Socioecological Model to capture both what safety issues matter most and how farmers prefer to learn about them. Categorical Principal Components Analysis and K-means clustering identified four distinct farmer profiles based on engagement preferences.

Key Findings

The two studies converge on findings that operate across multiple levels of the socioecological system, from individual farmer priorities to structural and policy-level constraints. This multi-level convergence reinforces the central finding that farm safety cannot be addressed through interventions at any single level alone.

At the individual level, farmers prioritise awareness and hazard elimination, 'Awareness of health and safety risks' was farmers' top-ranked safety priority, while 'safe machinery or equipment' ranked second. These findings confirm that farmers recognise the importance of both understanding risks and addressing them through higher levels of the Hierarchy of Controls—elimination and substitution of hazards through better equipment and work design/management.

At the interpersonal and community levels, diverse engagement approaches are essential. One-size-fits-all approaches to farm safety engagement will fail to reach substantial portions of the farming population. The identification of four distinct farmer profiles, each with different learning preferences, has direct implications for how Member States design and deliver farm safety services.

At the organisational and policy levels, structural constraints prevent farmers from acting on their safety priorities. Both studies identified that farmers, in general, know what they need to do but lack time and labour resources to implement improvements. 'Farmers forced to work ill and injured' emerged as a critical underpinning construct; correspondingly, 20% of surveyed farmers prioritised 'help on the farm or time to get everything done' alongside the adoption of practical solutions. The Priority Needs Register organised needs across four stakeholder groups—farmers/citizens, public organisations, research/education, and private sector—demonstrated the responsibilities of each group to the development and implementation of initiatives that overcome the structural challenges faced by farmers. The key point is that no single actor can address farm safety challenges alone.

Across all levels, safety culture emerges as foundational. Low management commitment and lack of safety culture on farms was the most frequently cited underpinning construct across all 11 CoPs. This suggests that technical solutions and equipment improvements, while necessary, are insufficient without attention to the cultural, and the associated structural underpinnings, dimensions that shape how safety knowledge is translated into practice across all socioecological levels.

Four Farmer Profiles

Cluster analysis identified four distinct farmer profiles distinguished by engagement preferences rather than demographic characteristics. These findings establish that farmers need to be reached through targeted and differentiated approaches if health or safety initiatives are to be effective:

- **Interpersonal Learners (40% of sample)** rely on personal social networks for acquisition of safety knowledge and prefer informal, relationship-based learning over formal organisational engagement. This is the single largest group within the data but currently receives only sporadic support, which has in most instances not been evaluated, across most Member States.
- **Knowledge First farmers (22% of sample)** focus on safety awareness and training through structured, didactic learning, showing a preference for classroom-based approaches and risk assessment tools.
- **Risk Preventers (20% of sample)** prioritise material resources, equipment, and engineering solutions rather than any specific engagement approach. They are best reached through investment mechanisms and practical support rather than educational programmes.
- **Organisational Learners (18% of sample)** actively engage with multiple organisations through structured learning environments while also valuing experiential application. This group is generally well-served by current advisory and extension services.

Policy Implications

The findings have direct relevance for ongoing policy discussions at EU and Member State levels.

For the current CAP period (2023-2027): Member States can integrate OSH into Farm Advisory Services without Strategic Plan amendment; utilise LEADER funding and EIP-AGRI mechanisms to establish Farm Safety Communities of Practice; and pilot community-embedded initiatives to reach, in particular, Interpersonal Learners through existing farmer-to-farmer networks. These initiatives could be further developed, scaled up and evaluated through the creation of an EU Thematic Network or an EU wide research project in this area.

For Post-2027 CAP integration: The proposed farm relief services provision (Article 17 of COM (2025) 560) should be utilised by Member States to enable farmers to attend safety training, implement

improvements, and recover from injuries. OSH should be integrated into the mandatory Generational Renewal Strategy, recognising that dangerous working conditions deter young people from entering agriculture. The AKIS description required in National Plans should explicitly address how services will reach farmers with different learning preferences.

For longer-term systemic change: Member States should evaluate their current farm safety service portfolios against the four farmer profiles to identify underserved populations. EU and national research should examine medium and long-term consequences of farm injuries on households and communities. Consideration should be given to how OSH protections can be extended or adapted for self-employed farmers, who currently fall outside the scope of EU OSH directives.

Recommendations

Three overarching recommendations emerge from synthesising both studies:

1. **Diversify engagement approaches to reach all farmer profiles.** Current farm safety systems primarily serve Organisational Learners and Knowledge First farmers through formal advisory and educational structures. The 40% of farmers identified as Interpersonal Learners require different approaches—peer networks, community-embedded initiatives, and integration of safety messaging into existing farmer-to-farmer knowledge exchange—that are currently sporadic and unevaluated. Member States should evaluate their service portfolios against the four profiles and develop differentiated strategies.
2. **Address time poverty and labour constraints directly.** Both studies demonstrate that farmers' capacity to implement safety improvements is constrained by labour shortages and time pressure, i.e. high workloads. The proposed Post-2027 CAP provision for farm relief services provides a mechanism to address this barrier. Finland's comprehensive replacement worker scheme offers an implementation model. Without addressing these structural constraints, investment in training and awareness will have reduced impact.
3. **Recognise farm safety as integral to social sustainability and generational renewal.** The underpinning constructs identified in Study 1—including sector attractiveness, generational renewal challenges, and working conditions—demonstrate that farm safety is connected to broader questions of agricultural sustainability. The Post-2027 CAP's emphasis on competitiveness and mandatory Generational Renewal Strategy provides an opportunity to integrate OSH systematically rather than treating it as a separate compliance domain.

Contribution to Expected Outcomes

This deliverable directly addresses Expected Outcomes established in the Horizon Europe call for research on farm safety and farmer/worker health. It provides evidence to *enhance understanding and awareness by policy makers, farmers' organisations, trade unions and health authorities* on the implications of occupational safety for the future of the sector. The tiered recommendations support *improved health, safety and labour conditions in farming through better performing European and national policy and legal frameworks*. The identification of four farmer profiles and associated engagement strategies provides a practical evidence base for Member States developing differentiated approaches to farm safety within existing and proposed CAP mechanisms.

1. Introduction

1.1 Background

Farmers and agricultural workers in the EU face a wide variety of safety and health risks in their working environment. Official Eurostat statistics indicate that during the past ten years, the average annual work-related injury rate was 1,653/100,000 for agricultural workers whilst the fatality rate was 4.1/100,000 (Eurostat, 2024). Recent research undertaken as part of the SafeHabitus project highlights that these figures underestimate the true level of injuries and fatalities on farms across the EU. Reinvee et al. (2024) estimated that the annual fatal rate was 70% higher at 545/100,000 and the average number of injuries was 206,000 per year, compared to the official figure of 126,817. The analysis established that wide differences between injury and fatality rates are due to the exclusion of self-employed farmers, lack of social insurance systems, different farm structures, and various difficulties in collecting data at the national level (Reinvee et al., 2024).

These figures indicate that farming is, at least, the third most dangerous occupation in the EU. The elevated risk associated with agricultural work is related to the complex interaction of hazards that distinguish farming from most other occupations. Machinery, particularly tractors, represents the leading cause of fatal and serious injuries in agriculture, with overturns, entanglements, and collisions accounting for a substantial proportion of farm deaths across Europe and globally (Rondelli et al., 2018). Livestock handling constitutes another major source of injury, with studies consistently identifying farm animals—especially cattle and horses—as significant contributors to both fatal and non-fatal incidents (Doughrate et al., 2009). Agricultural workers face simultaneous exposure to chemical, biological, and physical hazards, including pesticides, dusts, zoonotic diseases, and noise, with research demonstrating that such multiple exposures can compound health risks beyond those posed by individual hazards (Bertin et al., 2018). The physical demands of farm work, characterised by repetitive movements, awkward postures, and manual handling, contribute to high rates of musculoskeletal disorders across all farming sectors (Kolstrup, 2012). Climate change is intensifying occupational heat stress, with agricultural workers recognised as particularly vulnerable due to the strenuous and outdoor nature of their work (El Khayat et al., 2022). Beyond physical hazards, farmers experience elevated rates of psychological distress, with systematic reviews identifying financial pressures, climate variability, workload, and social isolation as key risk factors affecting mental health (Daghagh Yazd et al., 2019). This convergence of physical, environmental, and psychosocial risks—compounded by an ageing workforce, remote working locations, and variable working conditions—creates an occupational health profile of exceptional complexity.

1.1.1 The need for multi-actor responses

Whilst prevention programmes and policies have been implemented across Europe, injury and fatality rates remain persistently high (Rautiainen et al., 2008). This persistence reflects not a lack of effort but rather the complexity of the challenge. Farm safety cannot be improved through farmer behaviour change alone. The capacity of farmers to implement safer practices depends substantially on the support, resources, and regulatory frameworks provided by the wider agricultural system. Advisory and extension services shape farmers' knowledge and decision-making capabilities. Educational institutions—from agricultural colleges to university programmes—prepare the next generation with safety awareness and skills. Machinery manufacturers and suppliers determine the safety features embedded in equipment at the point of design and sale. Insurance and social security systems create incentives for risk reduction and provide support following injury. Policymakers establish regulatory requirements and allocate funding for safety improvements. Effective farm safety improvement therefore requires coordinated action across this network of actors, each contributing within their sphere of responsibility and influence.

Recent approaches to prevention have increasingly recognised the role of safety culture and societal factors as contributors to safety and health outcomes (Leppälä et al., 2021). These sociocultural

approaches acknowledge that safety behaviours are shaped by norms, peer influences, and community expectations—not merely individual knowledge or motivation. Such approaches may be especially important for reaching farmers who face significant barriers to implementing safer farming practices. For example, even in Finland—which has one of the most comprehensive safety support systems for farmers, including a worker-replacement scheme—farmers struggle to find the necessary resources to upgrade their farms and continue using older equipment (Kaustell et al., 2011). This is also true in countries with more decentralised advisory-based safety systems, such as Ireland, where farmers face complex cost-benefit analyses when making safety decisions and investments (Surendran et al., 2024).

1.1.2 Understanding farmer engagement preferences

Farmers are the primary managers of occupational safety and health on their holdings, and positive engagement at every level is vital to reduce risk (McNamara et al., 2021). Developing support and education systems that encourage OSH behaviours requires understanding how farmers prefer to receive information and assistance. However, farmers in Europe are often disengaged from formal health and safety services, facing rural geographies with unreliable service provision (O'Connor et al., 2025), traditionally stoic and/or masculine norms against help-seeking (Firnhaber et al., 2024), and a general lack of time and funds to access resources (Deliverable 3.2).

These patterns of disengagement highlight a critical point: even well-designed support services will fail if they do not align with how farmers actually wish to receive information and assistance. Understanding farmer preferences for engagement—and recognising that different farmer populations may have fundamentally different preferences—is essential for designing effective interventions. Evidence suggests that over 90% of workplace injuries include, among structural and systemic factors, behavioural causes (McNamara, 2014). Gaining positive rapport and consistent behavioural engagement in OSH (Teagasc, 2022) is therefore essential, but the methods through which this engagement is achieved must be tailored to farmer preferences if they are to succeed.

1.1.3 Scope of this report

Given this background, improving farm safety across Europe requires addressing three interconnected questions:

1. **What are the priority challenges?** What hazards, issues, and systemic barriers must be addressed, and how do these vary across different farming contexts?
2. **Who needs to act?** What roles should different actors—farmers, advisors, educators, industry, policymakers—play in addressing these challenges?
3. **How do farmers want to be supported?** What safety priorities do farmers themselves identify, and through what channels do they prefer to receive information and assistance?

The SafeHabitus project provides a framework for addressing these questions, bringing together researchers, advisors, farmers, and stakeholders through a multinational multi-actor approach to support the development of effective preventive approaches and the transition to social sustainability in farming. This report synthesises findings from two research activities conducted through the SafeHabitus Community of Practice (CoP) network across 11 European countries: Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Ireland, Lithuania, Poland, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, and Spain.

1.2 Response to SafeHabitus Work Package Tasks

This deliverable synthesises findings from three interrelated tasks within the SafeHabitus project, each contributing distinct but complementary evidence to inform farm health and safety policy and practice.

Task 2.2 (Fostering multi-actor innovation) established the foundation for this work through the systematic engagement of Communities of Practice across the 11 participating countries. Through a series of CoP meetings involving farmers, farmers' groups, producers' associations, extension agents,

and other rural professionals, Task 2.2 developed a Priority Needs Register by collecting, assessing, and prioritising grassroots needs related to farm health and safety. Study 1 of this deliverable presents the synthesis of this Priority Needs Register, documenting 229 specific hazards, issues, challenges, and needs identified through expert consultation. The register identifies priority issues across different stakeholder groups—farmers, public organisations, research and education sectors, and private organisations—directly responding to the task's objective of identifying critical issues and critical needs across the different CoPs.

Task 2.5 (Transnational Community of Practice Networking) facilitated cross-national learning and synthesis through transnational meetings where CoP administrators and representatives shared experiences and identified common challenges. The synthesis report of the Priority Needs Register, presented through these transnational networking activities, enabled identification of both shared patterns and context-specific variations in farm safety challenges across the participating countries. This deliverable draws on these transnational exchanges to present findings that reflect both European-level patterns and national-level specificities.

Task 3.4 (Co-designing approaches to increase engagement) addressed the critical question of how farmers prefer to engage with risk management processes. Study 2 of this deliverable presents results from the farmer and farm worker survey implemented across all 11 CoPs, which identified barriers to adoption of farm safety practices and preferred engagement approaches. The survey, grounded in the Hierarchy of Controls and informed by the Socioecological Model, collected ranked preference data from 1,078 respondents. The cluster analysis presented in this report identifies four distinct farmer profiles based on their safety priorities and engagement preferences, directly responding to the task's objective of providing a multi-national empirical evidence base on risk behaviour and engagement preferences among different demographic groups. The national-level evaluations conducted through CoP discussions, as specified in Stage 2 of Task 3.4, informed the country-specific analyses presented in Sections 10.3–10.10, where survey findings are evaluated against existing national support systems.

Together, these three tasks exemplify the SafeHabitus multi-actor approach, combining expert-identified priorities (Tasks 2.2 and 2.5) with end-user preferences (Task 3.4) to provide an evidence base for developing targeted, effective interventions.

1.3 Contribution to EU Expected Outcomes

This deliverable contributes to the Expected Outcomes established for the Horizon Europe call under which the SafeHabitus project was funded. The findings address these outcomes as follows:

EO1: Enhanced understanding and awareness by policy makers, farmers' organisations, trade unions and health authorities

The Priority Needs Register (Study 1) provides a systematic documentation of farm health and safety challenges across 11 European countries, identifying both specific hazards and the underpinning systemic factors—including safety culture challenges, workload pressures, and inadequate OSH education—that contribute to persistently high injury rates. The farmer engagement survey (Study 2) provides empirical evidence on how different farmer populations prefer to receive safety information and support, addressing a gap in current understanding. Together, these findings enhance awareness of both the diversity of challenges facing European farmers and the diversity of approaches required to address them. The identification of four distinct farmer profiles based on engagement preferences offers stakeholders responsible for or concerned with the health or safety of farmers a framework for understanding why uniform approaches to safety promotion may fail to reach substantial portions of the farming population.

EO2: Improved policy and governance frameworks favouring safer and more inclusive working environments

The deliverable identifies specific roles for different stakeholder groups in addressing farm safety challenges, recognising that effective improvement requires coordinated action across farmers, public organisations, research and education sectors, and private organisations. The national-level evaluations (Sections 10.3–10.10) assess how existing support systems in each participating country serve different farmer profiles, identifying gaps in current provision and opportunities for improvement. The recommendations presented in Section 11 draw on this evidence to propose differentiated strategies that can inform policy development at both national and European levels. In particular, the finding that 40% of surveyed farmers are Interpersonal Learners who prefer informal, peer-based learning highlights a systematic gap in current service provision that policy frameworks should address.

EO3: Improved health, safety and labour conditions in farming

The deliverable provides an evidence base for developing more effective interventions by identifying both what safety priorities farmers themselves hold and how they prefer to engage with safety information. The Priority Needs Register documents the systemic barriers—including labour shortages, time constraints, and financial pressures—that prevent or hinder farmers from implementing safety improvements, highlighting the need for complementary supports such as worker replacement schemes alongside funding for equipment upgrades. The farmer profiles identified through the cluster analysis enable targeting of interventions to population segments currently underserved by existing approaches, offering a pathway toward more inclusive safety promotion that reaches farmers with diverse learning preferences and risk management priorities.

1.4 Structure of this deliverable

This deliverable is structured as follows:

Study 1 (Section 2) presents the Priority Needs Register, synthesising the hazards, issues, challenges, and needs identified through the CoP network, along with the roles different actors could play in addressing them.

Study 2 (Sections 3) presents results from the cross-national survey of farmers', farmworkers', family members', and agricultural students' safety and engagement priorities, identifying distinct farmer profiles based on their preferred forms of support.

Section 4 draws on both studies to present general conclusions and recommendations for policy and practice.

2. Study 1: Priority Needs Register

2.1 Introduction

Agriculture remains one of the most hazardous occupational sectors globally, with persistently high rates of fatal and non-fatal injuries despite decades of prevention efforts (Surendran et al., 2025). Systematic reviews consistently identify vehicles and machinery, livestock, and chemical exposures as leading causes of farm injuries across developed agricultural economies (DeRoo & Rautiainen, 2000; Surendran et al., 2025). However, research increasingly demonstrates that the causes of farm injuries extend well beyond these immediate physical hazards to encompass complex interactions of individual, social, and structural factors.

Mohammadrezaei et al. (2023), analysed 274 fatal farm injuries in Ireland over a 14-year period and found that fatalities cluster into distinct profiles defined not only by hazard type but by victim characteristics including age, farm role, and enterprise type. Their analysis revealed that older farmers working alone on livestock enterprises face qualitatively different risk profiles than younger workers injured in machinery incidents, suggesting that effective prevention requires differentiated approaches tailored to specific farming contexts rather than generic safety messaging.

The persistence of farm injuries despite prevention campaigns has prompted researchers to examine the social and cultural dimensions of farm safety. Shortall et al. (2019) argue that farm accidents represent a "persistent social pattern" rooted in how farm families socialise members to accept danger as normal. Their qualitative research in Scotland found that danger is normalised within farm families, with children socialised from an early age to undertake risky behaviours as part of authentic farm identity. This socialisation occurs within a regulatory environment that grants agriculture exemptions not available to other occupations, tacitly reinforcing farmers' autonomy to make safety judgements that would be prohibited elsewhere.

These findings highlight a critical gap in much farm safety research and intervention: a predominant focus on individual-level factors (farmer knowledge, attitudes, behaviours) without adequate attention to the social, institutional, and policy contexts that shape farm safety outcomes. Lee et al. (2017) proposed applying the Socioecological Model (SEM) to agricultural safety, arguing that effective interventions require coordinated action across multiple levels: individual farmers and workers; family and peer networks; community organisations; institutional and industry actors; and policy frameworks. Their framework positions the farm worker within nested spheres of influence, recognising that individual safety behaviours are enabled or constrained by factors at each level.

Systematic reviews of farm safety interventions support this multi-level perspective. Surendran et al. (2025) reviewed interventions targeting farm machine safety and found that while various behaviour change techniques have been applied, enforcement of safety regulations remains difficult due to the decentralised nature of farm work, and educational interventions alone show limited effectiveness in changing behaviours or reducing injury rates. Earlier, DeRoo and Rautiainen (2000) found that multifaceted interventions combining environmental modifications, farm visits, and education showed more promise than single-component approaches, though few studies examined actual injury outcomes.

This evidence base suggests that improving farm safety and health requires action from multiple actors beyond the farm gate. Farmers require not only knowledge and equipment but supportive social networks, accessible services, appropriate regulatory frameworks, and economic conditions that enable safety investments. Public organisations shape the policy and funding environment;

research and education institutions generate and disseminate knowledge; private organisations develop technologies and provide services. Understanding the priority needs across these actor groups is therefore essential to developing effective, coordinated responses to farm safety challenges.

The Priority Needs Register described in this section applies this multi-actor perspective through a systematic process of identifying hazards, challenges, and needs across 11 European countries participating in the SafeHabitus project. By engaging Communities of Practice comprising farmers, researchers, advisors, and other stakeholders, this research captures both the specific hazards affecting different farming systems and the structural factors that enable or constrain safety improvements.

2.2 Objectives and Structure

This section of Deliverable 3.3 reports the findings from research undertaken within Task 2.2, that sought to identify priority farm safety and health needs through systematic consultation with Communities of Practice (CoPs) across 11 European countries. The specific objectives were:

1. To identify and categorise the principal safety and health hazards, challenges, and needs facing farmers and farm workers across diverse European agricultural systems.
2. To specify priority needs according to the actor groups with capacity to address them: farmers and citizens; public organisations; research and education institutions; and private organisations.
3. To identify underpinning constructs—the social, cultural, economic, and structural factors—that influence safety and health outcomes on farms.

The methodology (Section 2.3) describes the co-creation process through which CoP members identified hazards, which were then classified, prioritised, and linked to responsible actors. Section 2.4 presents the results, organised into safety hazards (2.4.1), health hazards (2.4.2), and the specific challenges facing vulnerable worker groups (2.4.3). Section 2.5 synthesises the underpinning constructs that emerged across CoPs as systemic factors influencing farm safety. Section 2.6 consolidates priority needs by stakeholder group, identifying the requirements, measures, and resources necessary to address safety challenges. Section 2.7 summarises national CoP priorities, with detailed country-level findings available in Annex 1. The discussion (Section 2.8) interprets these findings in relation to the multi-actor framework, and conclusions (Section 2.9) summarise the key implications for policy, practice, and research.

2.3. Methods

The Priority Needs Register was developed through a systematic co-creation process involving CoP members across the 11 participating countries. The process followed a structured framework moving from hazard identification through to the specification of priority needs by actor group (Figure 1). For an overview of the definition of the concepts used in the Needs Register, please see Annex 2.

WP2.2 Priority Needs Register: collecting, assessing and prioritising grass-root issues and needs

Figure 1 SafeHabitus priority needs data collection framework.

2.3.1 Conceptual Framework

The framework distinguished between immediate hazards and the broader factors shaping safety outcomes. Hazards were classified according to their characteristics to support prioritisation, assessment, and management. Injury hazards were categorised by source—physical, chemical, or biological—where acute injuries result from sudden unexpected incidents. Health hazards were similarly categorised but distinguished by longer-term exposures resulting in occupational disease or ill health (Langley & Brenner, 2004). A third category, underpinning constructs, captured social, cultural, economic, and structural factors that influence safety and health on farms but are not hazards in themselves.

For each hazard category, the framework required identification of critical issues (specific problems posing risk to safety and wellbeing); critical challenges (difficulties that must be addressed to improve the critical issue); and priority needs (essential requirements, measures, or resources necessary to address the challenges). Priority needs were classified according to the actor group best positioned to address them: farmers and citizen groups; public organisations; research and education institutions; and private organisations.

2.3.2 Data Collection

Data were collected using a structured template distributed to CoP network representatives with accompanying guidelines. The template required CoPs to document hazards, critical issues, challenges, and needs, distinguishing between physical safety hazards, health hazards, and underpinning constructs. CoPs were also asked to identify vulnerable or target populations at particular risk, including any gender-specific vulnerabilities.

All 11 CoP countries completed the template between March and April 2024. Two review rounds were conducted by the task leaders (LUKE) to clarify entries, resolve ambiguities, and ensure consistent application of the framework categories. CoPs were able to revise and supplement their initial submissions following feedback.

2.3.3 Analysis

The completed templates yielded 229 initial hazard and issue entries across the 11 countries. Many entries addressed similar or overlapping topics. The analysis proceeded in two stages. First, similar hazards were grouped into thematic categories through content analysis, reducing the initial entries to 13 topic categories covering both safety hazards (animal handling, machinery, chemicals, biological risks, working conditions and ergonomics, slips/trips/falls) and health hazards (mental health and wellbeing, working conditions and ergonomic risks, diseases and ill health). Second, the critical issues, challenges, and priority needs associated with each category were synthesised across countries, identifying both common patterns and country-specific variations.

The underpinning constructs identified by CoPs were analysed separately to capture systemic factors that cut across specific hazard categories. These were consolidated into key themes, with notation of which CoPs identified each construct.

2.3.4 Limitations

The Priority Needs Register captures expert and stakeholder perspectives on safety priorities within each CoP network. The composition of CoPs varied by country, reflecting different national configurations of farming organisations, research institutions, advisory services, and regulatory bodies. The findings therefore represent informed stakeholder judgement rather than epidemiological measurement of hazard prevalence or injury incidence. The register does not quantify the relative magnitude of different hazards, nor does it assess the effectiveness of existing interventions. Its purpose is to identify priority areas requiring attention from the perspective of those engaged with farm safety across diverse European contexts.

2.4. Results

All 11 CoPs submitted completed templates documenting hazards, critical issues, challenges, and priority needs. Table 1 summarises the distribution of entries across the three main categories.

Table 1 Number of hazards identified by CoPs

Issues	Number
Safety hazards	84
Health hazards	60
Underpinning constructs	85
Total	229

The 229 initial entries contained substantial overlap, with multiple CoPs identifying similar hazards and challenges. Through content analysis, these were consolidated into 13 thematic categories. The following sections present the principal findings for safety hazards, health hazards, and vulnerable worker groups. Underpinning constructs are addressed separately in Section 2.5, and the synthesis of priority needs by actor group is presented in Section 2.6.

2.4.1 Safety Hazards

Safety hazards were classified into physical, chemical, and biological categories. Physical hazards encompassed animal handling, machinery operation, and working environment concerns including ergonomic issues and slip, trip, and fall hazards. Table 2 presents the main safety hazard categories and associated challenges identified across CoPs.

Table 2 The main farm safety hazard issues and challenges reported by the CoPs

Safety hazard issues (number of issues named by CoPs)	Challenges and sources of safety hazards and injuries (Similar entries by CoPs are combined below)
Livestock Safety (16)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Animal aggression and sudden movement • Limited exit and escape routes in animal housing facilities • Animal handling skills and understanding livestock behaviour (Human-Animal Relations) • Handling and storing veterinary chemicals and medicines • Lack of PPE use • Slurry handling and manure gas exposure • Moving and transporting animals • Young and other vulnerable workers/bystanders
Machinery Safety (19)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Old or poorly maintained machines, including lack of machinery renewal and finance • Front-end loader and lifting equipment • Quad bikes • Lack of safety guards • Driving on public roads • Mobile phone use during operations • New technology and automation • Insufficient machinery safety skills Lack of PPE use • Children and bystander safety
Chemical Safety (19)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Chemical gases and vapours • Pesticide poisoning • Chemical storage safety • Insufficient training in chemical use • Lack of PPE use • Lack of first aid equipment/facilities/training • Children and bystander safety
Biological hazards (11)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Zoonosis risks • Respiratory problems • Insect and tick bites • Infectious diseases among workers • Lack of health screenings • Lack of PPE use
Working conditions, ergonomics, slips/trips/falls (17)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Working at heights • Slopes and uneven surfaces • Difficult and harmful postures • Extreme weather conditions (cold, ice, snow, heat, sun)
Other (2)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Visitor safety on farms • Safety where farm and home overlap

Animal handling, machinery, and chemical handling each generated substantial numbers of issues across CoPs, reflecting their status as leading causes of farm injuries across Europe. Certain hazards were identified by only one or two CoPs, reflecting specific national or regional contexts: extreme arctic conditions (Finland), child safety on farms (Ireland, Poland), risks from wild animals (Slovakia), mobile

phone use during farm operations (Germany), and quad bike safety (Ireland). This does not suggest that these issues are limited to these countries, rather, they reflect the difference in priorities amongst the different CoPs.

2.4.2 Health Hazards

Health hazards were organised into three primary categories: mental health and wellbeing; working conditions and ergonomic risks; and diseases and ill health (Table 3).

Table 3 Health hazard categories and challenges reported by CoPs

Health hazard issues (number of issues named by CoPs)	Challenges and sources of health hazards and injuries (Similar entries by CoPs are combined below)
Mental health and wellbeing (18)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identifying mental health symptoms • Lack of mental health services • Fatigue and lack of sleep • High workload, stress, and burnout • Technostress • Loneliness and social isolation • Masculine 'must be strong' culture • Anxiety and depression • Suicide • Use of alcohol and drugs • Lack of social networks and activities outside farming • Lack of self-respect and perceived disrespect from society • Cultural and language barriers among seasonal workers
Working conditions and ergonomic risks (12)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of ergonomic equipment • Noise exposure • Vibration exposure • Carpal tunnel syndrome from repetitive work • Musculoskeletal disorders • Handling digital tools during farm activities • Lack of PPE and safe working methods Inadequate ventilation in animal buildings • Extreme temperature exposure including climate-induced heat stress • Lack of time and rest
Diseases and ill health (17)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Working while ill due to lack of relief workers • Chronic diseases including heart disease and cancers • Hearing loss • Skin diseases and allergies • Respiratory diseases from dust and chemicals; zoonoses • Health decline among ageing farmers • Vibration syndromes • Alcohol and drug use • Lack of risk identification and awareness • Lack of PPE use • Lack of first aid provision

Mental health emerged as a prominent concern across CoPs, with 18 distinct issues identified. The challenges reflect both individual factors (stress, fatigue, substance use) and structural conditions (isolation, lack of services, societal attitudes toward farming). Working while ill was identified as a particular challenge in agriculture, as certain tasks—especially animal care—must be performed daily regardless of the farmer's health status.

2.4.3 Vulnerable Worker Groups

CoPs identified specific challenges affecting groups at heightened risk of injury or ill health on farms. These vulnerable groups included women, young people, children, elderly farmers, migrant and seasonal workers, and people with disabilities. Figure 2 summarises the distribution of challenges and needs across these groups.

Figure 2 Safety and health challenges and needs among vulnerable groups on farms

A total of 79 challenges and needs were identified relating to vulnerable groups. Key findings included:

- **Women and young people** share similar safety management considerations, particularly regarding training access and workplace integration.
- **Elderly and disabled farmers** face challenges related to physical capacity, with implications for workload management and farm infrastructure adaptation.
- **Children** require specific consideration in farm safety planning, as their presence during farm operations creates risks even when they are not directly engaged in work tasks.
- **Migrant and seasonal workers** face distinct challenges including language barriers, unfamiliarity with local practices and equipment, accommodation conditions, and access to health services.
- **Men** were identified by some CoPs as a vulnerable group in specific contexts, linked to attitudes and work cultures associated with elevated risk-taking.

2.4.4 Cross-Cutting Challenges

The hazard categories presented above are analytically distinct, but several challenges emerged repeatedly across multiple categories. Lack of PPE use, for instance, was identified as a challenge in relation to animal handling, machinery operation, chemical handling, biological hazards, and disease prevention. Similarly, training and skills deficits appeared across machinery, chemical, and animal handling categories, while working while ill or injured featured in both physical health and mental health contexts. Three factors may explain the repeated identification of certain challenges across hazard categories:

- First, some challenges are genuinely crosscutting in nature. PPE use, for example, is relevant wherever workers are exposed to physical, chemical, or biological hazards, though the specific equipment required differs by context. The repeated identification of PPE-related challenges across categories reflects the pervasive nature of this issue rather than analytical redundancy.
- Second, the co-creation methodology invited CoP members to identify challenges within predefined hazard categories. Where a challenge such as inadequate training affects multiple aspects of farm work, it would logically be reported under each relevant category. The methodology captured the breadth of contexts in which particular challenges manifest, rather than forcing premature aggregation.
- Third, and most significantly, the recurrence of certain challenges across categories suggests that these are not hazard-specific problems amenable to hazard-specific solutions. When the same underlying issues—inadequate training, insufficient resources, time pressures, lack of safety culture—appear repeatedly regardless of which hazard category is under consideration, this points toward systemic factors that shape safety outcomes across the farming enterprise as a whole. This interpretation is consistent with the socioecological perspective outlined in the introduction. Individual-level challenges such as PPE use or skill deficits do not exist in isolation; they are shaped by interpersonal norms, community practices, institutional supports, and policy frameworks. A farmer may lack appropriate PPE not due to personal negligence but because of cost constraints, limited availability in rural areas, discomfort that slows work under time pressure, absence of enforcement, or cultural norms that frame PPE use as unnecessary or even as a sign of weakness (Shortall et al., 2019).

Addressing such challenges therefore requires action beyond the individual farmer. The following section examines the underpinning constructs—the social, cultural, economic, and structural factors—that CoPs identified as shaping safety and health outcomes on farms. These constructs provide context for understanding why the cross-cutting challenges identified above persist despite widespread awareness of their importance.

2.5 Underpinning Constructs

Beyond specific hazards, CoPs identified systemic factors that shape safety and health outcomes across the farming enterprise. These underpinning constructs—social, cultural, economic, and structural in nature—provide context for understanding why many of the challenges identified in Section 3.4 persist despite widespread awareness of their importance. A total of 85 entries relating to underpinning constructs were reported, which consolidated into 12 principal themes. Table 4 summarises these constructs and indicates which CoPs identified each.

Two constructs—lack of safety culture and stress/high workload—were identified by all 11 CoPs, indicating their relevance across diverse European farming systems. Several other constructs were identified by seven or more CoPs, including lack of OSH education (7), need for risk identification (9), ageing and generation gap (7), lack of resources (7), and animal handling challenges (9).

Table 4 Underpinning constructs identified by CoPs

Construct	Description	CoPs
Lack of resources and funding	Farmers not investing in maintenance or safety due to financial insecurity; smaller farms unable to invest in technology or assistance; decreased profitability affecting safety priorities	Germany, Ireland, Lithuania, Poland, Romania, Slovakia, Spain
Hard working conditions	Lack of resources for improvement; challenging terrain (slopes, forests, wet surfaces); extreme weather; limited financial resources hindering investment in modern equipment	Estonia, Finland, Lithuania, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain
Labour shortages and workforce issues	Difficulty finding and retaining employees; unattractive salary and image; competition with other industries; dependency on migrant workers; emigration of agricultural workers	Estonia, Finland, Germany, Ireland, Slovakia, Spain
Stress and high workload	Farmers overworked and worried; putting farm and family wellbeing above personal wellbeing; not seeking help for health problems; fatigue, rushing, and associated injury risk	All CoPs
Working alone and social isolation	Decreasing farmer numbers in some areas; long distances and logistical problems; lack of immediate help if incidents occur; social isolation contributing to mental health risk; farmers feeling disrespected by society	Finland, France, Romania, Slovenia
Farmers working while ill or injured	No relief workers available; daily tasks (especially animal care) must be performed regardless of health status; long-term consequences for health and injury risk	Estonia, Finland, Slovenia
Ageing farmers and generation gap	Lack of succession affecting motivation to invest in safety; potential resistance of older farmers to new technologies; delayed succession straining family relationships; need to engage younger generation	Estonia, Finland, France, Ireland, Lithuania, Poland, Romania
Family issues and communication barriers	Farm family structures creating challenges; balancing work and family responsibilities; communication barriers about safety between family members; gendered dimensions of farm work and safety	Estonia, Finland, Germany, Ireland, Poland, Romania, Slovenia
OSH education in agriculture	Safety issues receive insufficient attention in agricultural education; gap in vocational training, agricultural schools, and universities; specific regulations for agriculture missing; lack of trainer training	Estonia, Finland, Germany, Poland, Romania, Slovakia, Spain
Safety culture	Poor farm management practices; traditional working habits resistant to change; low understanding of safety issues; lack of management commitment; formal safety procedures not followed; attitudes that underestimate the value of work safety	All CoPs
Awareness of farm safety risks	Lack of communication about safety risks; need for practical risk identification specific to farming contexts; inadequate risk assessment and management	Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Ireland, Lithuania, Romania, Slovakia, Spain
Safety challenges in animal handling	Lack of standardised protocols; need for training on animal behaviour and handling techniques; preventive measures during animal handling underdeveloped	Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Ireland, Lithuania, Poland, Romania, Slovakia

These constructs operate at multiple levels of the socioecological model. Some relate primarily to individual and interpersonal factors (stress, family communication), others to community and institutional contexts (isolation, education systems, labour markets), and others to broader policy and economic structures (funding, regulation, agricultural profitability). Critically, they help explain why individual-level challenges such as PPE use or machinery maintenance persist: farmers operate within social, economic, and institutional contexts that may constrain their capacity to adopt safer practices regardless of awareness or intention.

The construct of safety culture warrants particular attention given its identification by all CoPs. The challenges described—traditional habits resistant to change, attitudes undervaluing safety, lack of management commitment—reflect the normalisation of danger within farming that Shortall et al. (2019) identified in their analysis of why farm accidents persist. Changing safety culture requires intervention not only at the farm level but across the networks, institutions, and policy frameworks that shape farming practice.

2.6 Priority Needs by Stakeholder Group

The framework required CoPs to specify priority needs according to the actor group best positioned to address them. This section synthesises needs across all hazard and health categories, organised by the four stakeholder groups: farmers and citizens; public organisations; research and education institutions; and private organisations. Figure 3 provides a visual summary.

Figure 3 Summary of needs to address farm safety hazards, issues and challenges reported by CoPs

2.6.1 Farmers and Citizens

Needs identified for farmers and citizen centred on seven themes:

- **Stakeholder collaboration:** Engaging with advisory services, farming organisations, and peer networks.
- **Risk management and planning:** Conducting safety and health risk assessment/management, planning corrective actions, and support for implementing changes in practice.
- **Safety information and guidelines:** Accessing and applying safety guidelines, manuals, and best practices relevant to specific farm contexts and hazards.

- **Insurance coverage:** Maintaining insurance to cover occupational injury and illness risks.
- **Skills development:** Participating in training and education to develop safety-relevant competencies.
- **Personal protective equipment:** Using appropriate PPE for different tasks, with understanding of when and how to use it effectively.
- **Managing others' safety:** Ensuring safety of children, workers, elderly family members, and visitors on the farm.

These needs assume farmers have agency to act, but as the underpinning constructs indicate, this agency is constrained by time, resources, knowledge, and the broader systems within which farms operate.

2.6.2 Public Organisations

Needs relating to public organisations—including government agencies, regulatory bodies, and publicly funded services—encompassed:

- **Stakeholder coordination:** Facilitating collaboration between farmers, researchers, educators, and industry; promoting safety culture across the sector.
- **Funding and financial support:** Providing funding for safety training, equipment, research, and on-farm safety improvements; tax incentives for safety investments.
- **Social insurance systems:** Developing and maintaining social insurance arrangements that cover farm accidents and occupational illness.
- **Regulation and enforcement:** Establishing appropriate safety regulations for agricultural settings and ensuring compliance.
- **Service provision:** Organising practical workshops, events, and advisory services for farmers; developing farm relief worker systems.
- **Monitoring and surveillance:** Supporting data collection on farm injuries and occupational diseases to inform policy and target interventions.

The breadth of needs identified for public organisations reflects the extent to which farm safety depends on supportive policy frameworks, adequately resourced services, and functioning social protection systems.

2.6.3 Research and Education

Needs relating to research and education institutions included:

- **Stakeholder collaboration:** Working with farmers, industry, and policymakers to ensure research addresses practical needs and findings are translated into practice.
- **Knowledge generation:** Conducting research on safety and health risks, intervention effectiveness, behavioural factors with specific consideration given to social and cultural barriers to adoption, and emerging challenges.
- **Training and education:** Providing farm safety training at all levels—vocational, tertiary, and continuing education; developing curricula that integrate OSH into agricultural education; training trainers and advisors.
- **Innovation:** Developing new tools, technologies, and approaches to risk assessment and management.
- **Knowledge dissemination:** Creating accessible information materials, guidelines, and decision-support tools for farmers and advisors.

The identification of education-related needs by seven CoPs as an underpinning construct (Section 3.5) underscores the perceived gap between current educational provision and the knowledge and skills farmers require for effective safety management.

2.6.4 Private Organisations

Needs relating to private organisations—including machinery manufacturers, input suppliers, service providers, and insurers—encompassed:

- **Stakeholder collaboration:** Working with researchers and public agencies to improve safety outcomes across the sector.
- **Service provision:** Offering advisory services, farm visits, and safety consultations.
- **Information and demonstration:** Showcasing good practices; demonstrating safety equipment and its proper use.
- **Product training:** Providing effective safety training and orientation when selling machinery or equipment.
- **Technology development:** Developing and promoting safer machinery, equipment, and technologies.
- **Insurance products:** Developing insurance arrangements that incentivise safety improvements.

Private organisations interact with farmers through commercial relationships, creating opportunities to integrate safety considerations into product design, sales, and after-sales support. The identified needs suggest this potential is not fully realised.

2.6.5 Multi-Actor Coordination

The distribution of needs across all four stakeholder groups confirms that improving farm safety and health requires coordinated action rather than reliance on any single actor. Farmers require knowledge, resources, and supportive environments that depend substantially on the actions of public organisations, research and education institutions, and private industry. Equally, interventions by these actors will have limited impact without farmer engagement and uptake. The socioecological model's emphasis on multi-level, interacting influences applies directly: sustainable improvement in farm safety outcomes depends on alignment across individual, community, institutional, and policy levels.

2.7 National CoP Priorities

The 11 CoPs identified priority areas specific to their national contexts and network focus. Table 5 summarises the principal priorities for each country. The priorities reflect both common concerns and context-specific challenges. Safety culture, mental health, machinery safety, and animal handling appear as priorities across multiple countries. However, specific emphases differ: Spain's focus on migrant worker safety reflects the importance of seasonal labour in its horticultural sector; Finland's attention to occupational health services reflects its relatively developed social insurance infrastructure; Romania's emphasis on technological upgrading reflects the modernisation challenges facing its sheep farming sector.

When reviewing national priorities, it is important to recognise that CoP composition and focus influence what is identified as a priority. A CoP not focused on livestock production will not prioritise animal handling safety, regardless of its objective importance in that country. The priorities therefore represent informed stakeholder judgement within each CoP's scope rather than comprehensive national assessments. Detailed country-level findings, including specific challenges and proposed solutions, are presented in Annex 1.

Table 5 Summary of CoP priority focus areas by country

Country	CoP Focus	Principal Priorities
Estonia	Cattle and machinery safety	Safe animal handling; machinery safety guidelines; safety risk management; network development
Finland	Dairy farm safety and health management	Safety in animal handling; safety culture and attitudes; occupational health services; mental health and quality of life
France	Cattle farm safety and health	Psychosocial risk handling; one health management; safety knowledge development; farm ergonomics
Germany	Occupational health and safety in the green sector	Safety education; safety motivation; safe machinery handling; safety management; safety tool development
Ireland	Practical farm safety issues and safety culture	Machinery handling; livestock handling; work organisation; social sustainability; services for farmers
Lithuania	Safe working environment and safety culture	Mental stress handling; stakeholder network collaboration; safety education; working conditions and maintenance
Poland	Safety and health in individual farming	Systemic solutions for safety education; enhancing farmers' health and wellbeing; modern farming technologies; farm labour issues; mental health
Romania	Sheep farm safety and health	Improving safety education and training; technological upgrading; labour management; farmer health and safety support; mental health
Slovakia	Practical solutions to OHS challenges	Improving safety culture; tailored agriculture education; enhancing machinery safety; animal handling practices
Slovenia	Mental health awareness and support	Machinery safety; developing agriculture safety policy; psychosocial support for farmers, including farm relief services
Spain	Migrant farm worker safety (berry and citrus)	Ergonomics safety; work management; mental stress handling; accommodation for workers

2.8 Discussion

The Priority Needs Register documents 229 hazards, challenges, and needs identified through systematic consultation with CoPs across 11 European countries. While the specific hazards—animal handling, machinery operation, chemical exposure, mental health—are well established in the farm safety literature, the register's principal contribution lies in its multi-actor framing and its identification of underpinning constructs that shape safety outcomes.

2.8.1 Beyond Individual Deficits

The hazard categories presented in Section 3.4 are dominated by challenges framed at the individual or farm level: lack of PPE use, inadequate training, poor maintenance, working while ill. Such framings implicitly locate the problem with farmers—they lack something, they fail to do something, they use inadequate equipment. While these descriptions are not inaccurate, they are incomplete.

The underpinning constructs identified in Section 3.5 provide essential context. Farmers may not use PPE because of cost, discomfort, time pressure, or cultural norms that frame its use as unnecessary. They may lack training because OSH is inadequately integrated into agricultural education. They may continue using old machinery because they cannot afford replacement and lack access to finance. They

may work while ill because no relief worker system exists or labour is unavailable/unaffordable. In each case, the individual-level deficit reflects structural conditions beyond the individual farmer's control.

This interpretation aligns with Shortall et al.'s (2019) analysis of why farm accidents persist despite awareness raising initiatives, e.g. safety campaigns. Their research identified the normalisation of danger within farm families, where risk-taking is socialised as part of authentic farm identity, and regulatory frameworks grant agriculture exemptions that reinforce farmer autonomy over safety decisions. The universal identification of "lack of safety culture" as an underpinning construct by all 11 CoPs resonates with this analysis: safety culture is not simply an aggregate of individual attitudes but a collectively produced and institutionally reinforced pattern.

2.8.2 Multi-Level Intervention Requirements

The socioecological model posits that behaviour is shaped by multiple interacting levels of influence: individual, interpersonal, community, institutional, and policy (Lee et al., 2017). The Priority Needs Register findings support this framework. The recurrence of certain challenges—PPE use, training deficits, resource constraints—across multiple hazard categories (Section 3.4.4) suggests these are systemic issues requiring multi-level responses rather than hazard-specific interventions. A campaign promoting PPE use will have limited impact if farmers cannot afford appropriate equipment, find it impractical for their working conditions, or operate within a culture that stigmatises its use. Consequently, effective responses to the identified challenges are required at each level:

- **Individual level:** Farmers need knowledge, skills, and motivation to adopt safer practices. Training and education address this level.
- **Interpersonal level:** Family norms, peer influences, and advisor relationships shape safety behaviours. The identification of family communication barriers and the potential of peer networks point to intervention opportunities at this level.
- **Community level:** Local farming organisations, discussion groups, and advisory services provide contexts for knowledge exchange and norm development. Several CoPs emphasised the importance of farmer networks and community-based approaches.
- **Institutional level:** Education systems, advisory services, insurance arrangements, and industry practices create enabling or constraining conditions for farm safety. The needs identified for research/education and private organisations sit primarily at this level.
- **Policy level:** Regulation, funding, and social protection systems establish the framework within which all other levels operate. The substantial needs identified for public organisations reflect the foundational importance of supportive policy environments. Leadership of stakeholder co-ordination initiatives connecting across and within each of the SEM levels outlined above can be operationalised and sustained at the policy level.

2.8.3 Actor Interdependence

The distribution of needs across all four stakeholder groups confirms that no single actor can address farm safety challenges in isolation. Farmers depend on public organisations for regulatory frameworks, funding, and services; on research and education institutions for knowledge and training; and on private organisations for safe technologies and products. Equally, interventions by these actors depend on farmer engagement for their effectiveness.

This interdependence has implications for how safety improvement is conceptualised and pursued. Approaches that focus primarily on changing farmer behaviour—through information provision, training, or persuasion—address only one element of a multi-level system. The SafeHabitus Needs Register suggests that equal attention is required to the institutional, economic, and policy conditions that enable or constrain farmer action.

2.8.4 Variations Across Contexts

While common themes emerged across CoPs, the register also documents context-specific challenges reflecting different agricultural systems, labour arrangements, regulatory environments, and service infrastructures across Europe. Spain's focus on migrant worker safety, Finland's attention to relief worker systems, and Romania's emphasis on technological modernisation reflect genuine differences in priority needs.

This variation cautions against one-size-fits-all approaches to farm safety improvement or support for farmer health. Effective interventions must be tailored to specific contexts while drawing on transferable principles and evidence. The CoP model provides a mechanism for this contextualisation, enabling local stakeholders to identify priorities relevant to their circumstances while participating in cross-national learning.

2.9 Conclusions

The Priority Needs Register documents the safety and health challenges facing farmers and farm workers across 11 European countries, as identified through systematic consultation with Communities of Practice. The 229 entries consolidated into categories covering physical safety hazards, health hazards, vulnerable worker groups, and underpinning constructs.

The findings confirm well-established hazard categories—animal handling, machinery, chemicals, mental health—while highlighting the systemic factors that sustain these challenges. The identification of safety culture and stress/workload as common underpinning constructs, alongside widespread recognition of educational gaps, resource constraints, and workforce challenges, points to the structural conditions within which farm safety outcomes are produced. Based on this conclusion, three key implications emerge:

- First, improving farm safety requires coordinated action across multiple actor groups. The needs identified span farmers, public organisations, research and education institutions, and private industry. No single actor can address the identified challenges in isolation; progress depends on alignment across the system.
- Second, interventions focused solely on individual farmer behaviour will have limited impact without attention to the structural conditions that shape behaviour. The recurrence of challenges such as PPE use and training deficits across multiple hazard categories suggests these are systemic issues requiring multi-level responses.
- Third, while common priorities emerged across CoPs, context-specific challenges require tailored approaches. Effective knowledge exchange involves identifying transferable principles while adapting implementation to local circumstances.

The Priority Needs Register provides an evidence base for subsequent SafeHabitus work packages focused on developing and evaluating interventions, engaging policy stakeholders, and supporting knowledge exchange across European farming communities. Its principal value lies not in cataloguing hazards—which are already well documented—but in specifying the multi-actor needs and systemic factors that must be addressed if farm safety and health outcomes are to improve.

3. Study 2: Farmer Safety and Engagement Priorities

3.1 Introduction

This deliverable synthesises findings from 11 European countries: Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Ireland, Lithuania, Poland, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, and Spain. By analysing data from these diverse national contexts together, then applying findings to individual countries' current engagement options, this work identifies both shared patterns and context-specific variations in farmer safety priorities and engagement preferences.

Task 3.4 was originally design to co-design, develop, and test methods that increase farmer and farmworker engagement with risk management processes across the 11 SafeHabitus Communities of Practice. This was to proceed in two stages: first, CoPs would analyse survivor story videos generated in Task 3.2 to establish methods of improving engagement with risk management processes; second, CoPs would evaluate these methods, identify additional approaches, and describe these in EIP Practice Abstracts. Following recommendations from the SafeHabitus Ethics Mentor and with the agreement of the EU REA Project Officer, the decision was taken not to proceed with the collection of survivor stories videos (see Deliverable 8.1). This necessitated adapting the approach to Task 3.4 while preserving its core objective: collaborating with CoPs to understand how farmers, farmworkers, and agricultural students engage with risk management processes.

Rather than assessing the efficacy of survivor story videos, we designed a cross-national survey to establish an empirical evidence base on farmer safety priorities and engagement preferences. This approach generates primary data directly from end-users, providing insights for intervention design and the improvement of farming governance and health and safety service provision across Europe. The survey was designed and piloted by Teagasc (Task Leader) and implemented by the 11 CoP administrators.

A note on conceptual framing is warranted. The revised approach originally conceptualised this research as identifying "barriers to adopting farm safety practices" and "supports that will enable farmers/farmworkers to overcome these barriers." During survey development and piloting, we evolved this framing toward identifying farmer "priorities" and "preferences." This shift reflects a strengths-based research philosophy: rather than asking farmers what prevents them from being safe (a deficit framing that risks alienating respondents and generating socially desirable responses), we ask what they value most and how they prefer to learn. Barriers can be inferred from the gap between stated priorities and current system provision—a farmer who prioritises awareness but who perceives a lack of accessible training reveals a systemic barrier without being asked about which could be considered 'personal' failings.

This approach aligns with SafeHabitus' multi-actor philosophy, which positions farmers as experts in their own needs who require effective multi-actor support systems that enable them to adopt safer farming practices. By identifying groups of farmers based on their preferred engagement approaches, this research aims to inform policy development, advisory and extension practice, and research directions to ensure the social sustainability of the European agricultural sector.

3.2 Objectives

This study addressed two primary objectives:

1. Identify the safety and engagement preferences of farmers, farmworkers, farming family members, and agricultural students across the 11 SafeHabitus CoP countries.
2. Identify groups of participants that could be served by specific health and safety approaches based on their similar preferences, enabling targeted rather than one-size-fits-all interventions.

Objective 1 was accomplished through cross-national survey data collection, with combined results reported in Section 3.5.1. Objective 2 was accomplished through cluster analysis to identify how participants' preferences could allow services and awareness raising or education and training materials to be tailored to distinct farmer profiles, with results reported in Section 3.5.2.

3.3 Methods

3.3.1 Survey Development

Question 1: Farm Safety Priorities

Our theoretical foundation for Question 1 was the Hierarchy of Controls (HOC; Albus et al., 1980), a widely applied framework across Europe (EU-OSHA) and internationally for understanding risk management as driven by systemic improvements rather than solely individual action. The standard HOC positions elimination of hazards as most effective, followed by substitution, engineering controls, administrative controls, and personal protective equipment (PPE) as least effective.

We adapted the HOC framework to capture the social nature of farm safety identified both in our cohort of CoPs via the Priority Needs Register (Study 1) and consistently across the scientific literature (Shortall et al., 2019; Mohammadrezaei et al., 2023). First, based on the needs identified by CoPs, we collapsed the levels of 'engineering controls' and 'substitution' into a single item regarding upgrading farm machinery and infrastructure. Second, we expanded 'administrative controls' into two items due to the frequently distinguished difference between farmer workloads/staffing issues and actual training/knowledge requirements. Third, we added two dimensions that are not present in the standard HOC: risk awareness and interpersonal support.

We positioned Awareness at the first level of the hierarchy, conceptualising it as an enabling factor for all subsequent risk controls. We conceptualised Interpersonal Support as the encouragement and guidance that family and friends contribute to making farming safer—distinct from safety awareness specifically and often relating to engagement in safer farming practices. We positioned this above PPE (an example of a safe farming practice) and below administrative controls (where management of direct labour contributions from family or friends would lie).

Question 2: Engagement Preferences

Question 2 was designed to capture the variety of engagement approaches used across the 11 SafeHabitus CoP countries. Initial question design was informed by the Diffusion of Innovation Model (DOI; Aviles, 2020), which categorises populations by their adoption timing and preferred information sources. However, during analysis we identified limitations in applying DOI as our primary interpretive framework. DOI inherently privileges engagement with formal organisations and positions farmers who rely on informal networks as "laggards"—a framing that pathologizes legitimate and effective learning strategies (Vanclay, 2011). Given our finding that 40% of surveyed farmers prefer informal, relationship-based learning (Group 1: Interpersonal Learners), applying DOI would mischaracterise a substantial portion of our sample as deficient rather than engaging with farm safety through informal processes/structures.

We therefore adopted the Socioecological Model (SEM; Kilanowski, 2017) as our primary interpretive framework. SEM conceptualises behaviour as shaped by multiple nested levels of influence—individual, interpersonal, organisational, community, and policy—without privileging any single level as inherently superior. This framework allows us to characterise farmer groups by their preferred level of engagement

rather than by their position on an adoption curve, generating findings that inform differentiated engagement strategies rather than efforts to "convert" informal learners into formal ones. We retain DOI terminology where useful for comparison with existing literature, while applying the SEM framework and associated logic to our core interpretations.

3.3.2 Survey Structure

The final survey consisted of three sections (Annex 3). Table 6 presents the theoretical basis for each item.

- **Question 1** asked participants: "In your opinion, what are the highest priorities for making a farm safer?" Participants ranked seven options from 1 (highest priority) to 7 (lowest priority), with an additional 'other' option for open responses.
- **Question 2** asked participants: "How would you prefer to learn about farm safety?" Participants ranked seven engagement methods from 1 (most preferred) to 7 (least preferred), with an additional 'other' option.
- **Question 3** collected demographic information: age (six categories from 15-24 to 65+), gender, farm occupation (farm manager/owner/operator, farm worker/employee, farm family member, or agricultural student), farm enterprise type (eight categories based on Eurostat farm typology), total area farmed (hectares), and survey location (e.g. training course/lecture, demonstration event, or agricultural event).

Table 6 Theoretical Basis for Survey Items

	HOC / SEM Basis	Question Text
Q1	In your opinion, what are the highest priorities for making a farm safer?	
1.	Awareness of farm risk mitigation	Awareness of health and safety risks in farming
2.	Elimination of the risk entirely	Safe equipment and machinery
3.	Substitution / Engineering of less risky equipment or practices	Money to upgrade buildings / farmyard / machinery
4.	Administrative changes to personnel / work organisation	Help on the farm or time to get everything done
5.	Capacity growth of staff skills / knowledge	Training or support from advisors / farming organisations
6.	Support to farm safe and manage risk	Support to farm safely from family, friends, and important others
7.	PPE use and other individual behaviours	Personal protection use (Hi-vis jackets, eyewear, helmets, etc.)
Q2	How would you prefer to learn about farm safety?	
1.	Organisational Policy/Governance	In a training course/classroom
2.	Organisational Community	Talking with other farmers and specialists such as in a discussion group
3.	Interpersonal Organisational	One-to-one support from an advisor / specialist, e.g. vet or contractor
4.	Interpersonal	Talking with family and friends
5.	Individual Community	Reading about it in the agri-media / on social media
6.	Individual Organisational	Through an easy-to-use risk assessment tool, e.g. booklet or online app
7.	Individual	Learning on the job or through experience

3.3.3 Ethical Approval

Prior to data collection, institutional ethical approval was obtained from the Teagasc Social Research Ethics Committee. This approval covered all data collection, handling, storage, and related activities across all CoP partners as detailed in Deliverable 7.2. The ethics application covered both online and in-person data collection contexts to allow partner flexibility and regional adaptation of methodology. Participation was voluntary, anonymous, and confidential. Participants could withdraw at any time during survey completion; withdrawal after completion was not possible as data were fully anonymised and therefore impossible to identify from the larger sample.

3.4 Data Collection

3.4.1 Coordination and Training

Teagasc coordinated the multi-country data collection process through a structured support system. On 14 February 2025, Teagasc held an online Clinic to present the task methodology, address partner questions, and incorporate feedback. Following the Clinic, all CoP administrators received a comprehensive *Guidance Document* containing: the survey questionnaire, consent form templates (Annex 4), an analytical Excel spreadsheet with automated calculations, sampling guidance, and a reporting template for the development of Technical Notes – See SafeHabitus Deliverable 1.6.

CoP administrators were encouraged to maintain communication with Teagasc throughout data collection to ensure research activities satisfied central research objectives while allowing regional adaptation within established ethical guidelines.

3.4.2 Translation Process

CoP administrators translated the survey text and consent materials into their respective national languages. Translation guidance emphasised preserving meaning rather than literal word-for-word translation. Administrators were instructed to adapt safety systems and engagement options to local equivalents where necessary. For example, if a country lacked professional farm advisors equivalent to those in Ireland, the relevant question could be reworded to focus on one-to-one advice from locally relevant specialists. All substantive translation decisions were documented for methodological transparency and reported in country-level Technical Notes.

3.4.3 Target Population

The survey targeted adults (18 years and older) who contribute to farm work or are likely to do so in the future. This intentionally broad sampling frame was designed to maximise accessibility for CoP administrators while capturing diverse perspectives within the farming population. Eligible participants included:

- Farm owners, operators, and managers of any farm type
- Farm employees contributing to farm work (permanent, full-time, part-time, migrant, or seasonal workers)
- Farm family members who contribute to farm work (e.g. farm spouses or adult children)
- Agricultural students who contribute to farm work

Advisors and specialists who support farmers but do not directly contribute to farm work (such as agricultural advisors, builders, and veterinarians) were excluded from the sample.

3.4.4 Sampling and Recruitment

CoP administrators identified populations to which they had easiest access and designed recruitment strategies accordingly. Administrators were not required to target every eligible group or ensure representative sampling. This pragmatic approach recognised the varying capacities and networks of different CoPs while ensuring sufficient data collection across the consortium.

Data collection methods included:

- **In-person distribution:** Surveys were administered at agricultural college classes, farmer discussion groups (general and young-farmer focused), agricultural fairs, exhibitions, and field demonstrations. This method enabled direct engagement with target populations and immediate clarification of any questions.
- **Online distribution:** Where appropriate, CoPs deployed online surveys through EU Survey to ensure GDPR compliance. Online surveys included consent materials as part of the introduction. CoP administrators were advised that online surveys require clear communication and dissemination strategies to reach target populations effectively.
- **Mail distribution:** Some CoPs distributed surveys by post to reach farmers in remote areas or those less likely to attend events.

Each CoP was required to collect a minimum of 50 completed surveys (at least one answer per question), with additional responses encouraged where feasible.

3.4.5 Data Collection Timeline

Data collection took place between February - June 2025 (Months 26-30 of the project). Preliminary results were returned to Teagasc by mid-May 2025 for partners using online surveys and by end of May 2025 for partners using exclusively physical surveys. This staggered timeline allowed Teagasc to input online data into standardised Excel templates and return these to partners for CoP evaluation meetings.

3.4.6 Limitations

Based on the approach outlined in this section, there are several methodological limitations that should be considered when interpreting the findings presented below.

Sampling and representativeness. The study employed a convenience sampling approach, with CoP administrators targeting populations to which they had easiest access rather than implementing probability-based sampling. Consequently, the sample should not be interpreted as statistically representative of the European farming population. The pragmatic minimum threshold of 50 responses per country, while ensuring cross-national coverage, resulted in variable sample sizes that limit country-level comparisons. The substantial proportion of agricultural students and farm family members in the sample (38% combined) may weight findings toward perspectives of those entering or peripherally involved in farming, rather than established farm operators. Similarly, recruitment through agricultural events, discussion groups, and training courses may have oversampled farmers already engaged with formal agricultural networks—potentially underrepresenting the very "Interpersonal Learners" the analysis identifies as underserved.

Survey instrument constraints. The forced-ranking format, while analytically useful for differentiation, required participants to make trade-offs that may not reflect their actual preferences—a farmer may genuinely value multiple safety priorities or engagement methods equally. The seven-item structure for each question, though theoretically grounded, necessarily excluded other potentially important safety priorities (e.g., specific hazard types such as chemical exposure) and engagement methods (e.g., regulatory inspection, insurance incentives). The adapted Hierarchy of Controls framework, while appropriate for the research context, represents a modification of the standard framework that limits direct comparability with studies using conventional HOC operationalisations.

Translation and cross-cultural equivalence. While translation guidance emphasised preserving meaning rather than literal translation, and substantive adaptations were documented, formal back-translation or cognitive interviewing was not conducted. Concepts such as "discussion groups" or "agricultural advisors" may carry different connotations across agricultural systems, potentially affecting cross-national comparability. The allowance for local adaptation of items, while methodologically pragmatic, introduces variation that complicates pooled analysis.

Analytical considerations. The cluster analysis identified four farmer profiles based on the specific five-dimension structure extracted through CATPCA. Different dimensional solutions or clustering algorithms might yield alternative groupings. The four-cluster solution, while statistically supported and

interpretable, represents one of several possible segmentations of farmer preferences. The absence of significant demographic differences across clusters, while substantively interesting, may partly reflect limited statistical power for detecting such associations given the sample size distribution across demographic categories. Additionally, the cross-sectional design captures preferences at a single point in time; farmer engagement preferences may evolve with experience, life stage, or changing agricultural contexts.

Scope of inference. The findings describe stated preferences for engagement approaches rather than observed engagement behaviours or intervention outcomes. Whether farmers who express preference for peer-based learning actually learn more effectively through such approaches, or whether matching engagement strategies to preferences improves safety outcomes, requires evaluation research beyond the scope of this study. The four farmer profiles should be understood as heuristic categories useful for differentiating engagement strategies rather than as fixed typologies into which individual farmers can be definitively classified.

3.5 Data Analysis

3.5.1 Data Preparation

The final dataset contained 1,195 responses from across the 11 participating countries. Prior to analysis, data were cleaned and prepared following a standardised protocol. Cases with incomplete rankings (missing values) or duplicated rankings (tied ranks across the 14 items) were excluded, resulting in the removal of 116 cases (9.7% of the original sample). One duplicate response was removed. Ranking data were inspected for completeness and quality. The final analytical sample comprised 1,078 respondents. Table 7 presents the full demographic characteristics of the analytical sample.

Table 7 Full descriptives [post cleaning]

Variable	Category	Number	% Valid Sample
Gender	Male	595	56.40
	Female	460	43.60
Age	15-24	194	18.00
	25-34	179	16.60
	35-44	271	25.20
	45-54	239	22.20
	55+	193	18.00
Occupation/Role	Farm manager owner operator	540	50.10
	Farm worker employee	128	11.90
	Family Member or Student	410	38.00
Farm Type	Field Crops	195	18.70
	Horticulture	58	5.60
	Permanent Crops	42	4.00
	Grazing Livestock	328	31.40
	Granivores	42	4.00
	Mixed Cropping	115	11.00
	Mixed Livestock	39	3.70
	Mixed Crops/Livestock	226	21.60
Farm Size	<10	338	35.50
	10-49	176	18.50
	50-99	122	12.80

	100+	316	33.20
	Missing	126	

Note: Missing data for farm size accounted for 11.7% of the total sample, missing for all other variables ranged from 2 – 33 cases

Variable transformation: All single-item measures were transformed into categorical variables for analysis. To address sparse distribution in several preliminary categories, Farm Size and Age categories were collapsed to reduce small cells. Farm Occupation items (farm family member and agricultural student) were merged due to substantial overlap in responses and characteristics. Farm Type responses with multiple selections were recategorised into the relevant combined option. "Other" responses were screened and categorised into existing categories where possible; where this was not feasible, these were coded as missing due to small sample sizes.

3.5.2 Principal Components and Clustering Analytical Approach

Analysis proceeded in two stages to address the study objectives. Stage 1 employed dimensionality reduction to identify underlying preference structures; Stage 2 applied cluster analysis to identify distinct farmer profiles based on these preference structures.

Stage 1: Categorical Principal Components Analysis (CATPCA)

CATPCA was used to reduce the 14 ranked items (7 from Q1, 7 from Q2) into a smaller set of latent dimensions. CATPCA was selected over standard linear PCA due to the ordinal nature of ranking variables, which violate the interval-level measurement assumption of linear PCA. Optimal scaling in CATPCA preserves ordinality while estimating monotonic transformations that maximise explained variance and capture potential non-linear relationships among items (Linting et al., 2012).

Separate CATPCA analyses were conducted for Q1 (safety priorities) and Q2 (engagement preferences), with one- to three-dimension solutions examined for each item set. Dimensionality decisions were guided by multiple criteria: eigenvalue magnitude and total variance explained, Cronbach's alpha for internal consistency, component loading patterns, scree plot inspection, and theoretical interpretability of solutions (Linting et al., 2012). Component loadings were evaluated using a practical threshold of ≥ 0.40 (Hair et al., 2019). Internal consistency was assessed using Cronbach's alpha, with values ≥ 0.70 treated as acceptable for exploratory work (Nunnally & Bernstein, 1994).

For Q1, a two-dimension solution was retained, explaining 51.9% of total variance with good internal consistency ($\alpha = .845$). For Q2, a three-dimension solution was retained, explaining 62.6% of variance with good internal consistency ($\alpha = .900$). Alternative dimensional solutions offered less interpretable or less stable loading structures. Object scores for each retained dimension were extracted for subsequent clustering. Outlier screening based on object scores revealed no observations exceeding ± 3.5 standard deviations.

Stage 2: K-means Clustering

K-means clustering was applied to the five CATPCA dimension scores (two from Q1, three from Q2) using Euclidean distance to identify groups of respondents with similar prioritisation patterns. Because CATPCA produces centred and optimally scaled scores, no further standardisation was required prior to clustering.

Solutions ranging from $k = 3$ to $k = 6$ clusters were examined. Selection of the final solution was informed by inspection of the elbow plot of within-cluster sum of squares (WCSS), evaluation of cluster distinctiveness through ANOVA on dimension scores, interpretability of emerging patterns, and balance of cluster sizes (Hair et al., 2019). A four-cluster solution was retained as reductions in WCSS became

progressively smaller beyond this point, and the four-cluster solution produced interpretable and meaningfully distinct profiles.

Cluster separation was confirmed through ANOVA, which indicated significant differences across clusters on all five CATPCA dimensions. Interpretation of clusters was guided by the polarity of CATPCA dimensions as defined by their loading structures, and by the signs and magnitudes of cluster centres. This approach enabled characterisation of distinct safety prioritisation and engagement preference profiles.

3.5.3 Demographic Analysis

Differences in demographic characteristics across clusters were examined using chi-square tests to assess whether cluster membership was associated with observable respondent characteristics (age, gender, farm occupation, farm type, farm size). Effect sizes were evaluated using Cramér's V, with values below 0.10 considered trivial, 0.10–0.30 small, 0.30–0.50 moderate, and above 0.50 large. All analyses were conducted in IBM SPSS Statistics v29 and Microsoft Excel.

3.6 Results

3.6.1 Mean Scores

We first identified mean scores, displayed below in Table 8, with lower scores representing higher mean ranks (i.e. closer to 1) or a more positive response to the question. For Question 1, the mean ranking scores for each item show a clear priority on Awareness, followed by Safe Machinery and PPE use. Other farm safety issues were lower priorities on average. For Question 2, peer/discussion group, classroom, and specialist support were very close engagement priorities, while talking with family and risk assessment tools were clear lower priority methods.

Table 8 Mean results of questionnaire items

Question	Item	Mean Score
Q1a	Awareness of health and safety risks in farming	2.76
Q1b	Safe machinery or equipment	3.14
Q1c	Personal protection use (Hi-vis jackets, eyewear, helmets, etc.)	3.33
Q1d	Help on the farm or time to get everything done	4.31
Q1e	Money to upgrade buildings / farmyard / machinery	4.24
Q1f	Training or support from advisors / farming organisations	4.50
Q1g	Support to farm safely from family, friends, and important others	4.68
Q1h	Talking with other farmers and specialists such as in a discussion group	2.89
Q1i	In a training course/classroom	2.93
Q1j	One-to-one support from an advisor / specialist, e.g. vet or contractor	3.05
Q2a	Learning on the job or through experience	3.81
Q2b	Reading about it in the agri-media / on social media	4.36
Q2c	Talking with family and friends	5.01
Q2d	Through an easy-to-use risk assessment tool, e.g. booklet or online app	5.01

For Question 1 (farm safety priorities), 'Awareness of health and safety risks in farming' emerged as the highest priority among respondents (mean = 2.76), followed by 'Safe machinery or equipment' (3.14) and 'Personal protection use' (3.33). These three items were clearly distinguished from the remaining four, which clustered between 4.24 and 4.68. 'Support to farm safely from family, friends, and important others' ranked lowest (4.68), suggesting that while interpersonal support is valued, farmers prioritise risk awareness, equipment safety, and personal protection when considering what makes a farm safer.

For Question 2 (engagement preferences), three methods emerged as joint top priorities: 'Talking with other farmers and specialists such as in a discussion group' (2.89), 'In a training course/classroom' (2.93), and 'One-to-one support from an advisor/specialist' (3.05). Items such as 'Learning on the job or through experience' (3.81) and 'Reading about it in the agri-media/on social media' (4.36) occupied middle positions, reflecting moderate but not strong preferences. 'Talking with family and friends' and 'Through an easy-to-use risk assessment tool' were joint lowest priorities (both 5.01). However, as the cluster analysis reveals, these aggregate means obscure important variation—items ranking lower on average were key preferences for specific subgroups of farmers.

3.6.2 Cluster Analysis

Scree plots for both item sets are displayed in Figure 4. Neither plot showed a sharply defined inflection point; therefore, dimensionality decisions were guided primarily by variance explained, loading patterns, and interpretability. For Q1 (farm safety priorities), a two-dimension solution was retained, explaining 51.9% of total variance with good internal consistency ($\alpha = .845$). For Q2 (engagement preferences), a three-dimension solution was retained, explaining 62.5% of variance with good internal consistency ($\alpha = .900$). Alternative dimensional solutions offered less interpretable or less stable loading structures. Eigenvalues and variance statistics for retained solutions are reported in Table 9 and 10.

Figure 4 Scree plots for CATPCA dimensions (Q1 & Q2)

Tables 9 and 10 present the scores associated with each dimension. The further these numbers are from zero, the stronger each response is represented by this dimension, and therefore the more relevant these items are to interpret this dimension. For interpretation, we established labels for each dimension to capture the contrast between items at either end of the continuum, as explained in Table 11 below.

K means Clustering results

K-means clustering was applied to the five CATPCA dimension scores to identify groups of respondents with similar prioritisation patterns. The within-cluster sum of squares (WCSS) plot did not display a clear elbow (Figure 5); however, reductions in within-cluster variance became progressively smaller after the four-cluster solution. Given this pattern, alongside considerations of interpretability and cluster size balance, a four-cluster solution was retained. Cluster sizes and centres are displayed in Table 12 and Figure 6.

Table 9 CATPCA Variance and Loadings for Q1

	Eigenvalue	% Variance Explained
Dimension 1	2.169	30.979
Dimension 2	1.464	20.909
Total	3.632	51.888
Ranking Item	Dim 1	Dim 2
Money to upgrade buildings / farmyard / machinery	.732	-.176
Awareness of health and safety risks in farming	-.663	-.193
Help on the farm or time to get everything done	.633	.424
Personal protection use (Hi-vis jackets, eyewear, helmets, etc.)	-.586	-.295
Training or support from advisors / farming organisations	-.505	.009
Support to farm safely from family, friends, and important others	-.209	.810
Safe machinery or equipment	.388	-.688

Table 10 CATPCA Variance and Loadings for Q2

	Eigenvalue	% Variance Explained	
Dimension 1	1.692	24.168	
Dimension 2	1.425	20.354	
Dimension 3	1.258	17.976	
Total	4.375	62.498	
Ranking Item	Dim 1	Dim 2	Dim 3
One-to-one support from an advisor / specialist	-.620	.305	-.316
In a training course/classroom	-.618	-.510	-.213
Talking with family and friends	.603	.475	.163
Talking with other farmers and specialists	-.169	.719	-.052
Through an easy-to-use risk assessment tool	.447	-.568	.138
Reading about it in the agri-media / on social media	-.219	-.023	.853
Learning on the job or through experience	.534	-.079	-.580

Table 11 Dimension Labelling

	Question Label	Justification
Q1	In your opinion, what are the highest priorities for making a farm safer?	
Dim. 1	Material - Practice	Safety through maintaining material/capital capacity (money, labour, equipment) <-> maintaining safe practices (awareness, PPE, training)
Dim. 2	People - Equipment	Safety through managing people and social connections (family and labour) <-> managing equipment (machinery, PPE use)
Q2	In your opinion, what are the highest priorities for making a farm safer?	
Dim. 1	Informal - Formal	Engagement through informal learning channels (family and friends, on the job, tools) <-> formal learning channels (advisors and classrooms)
Dim. 2	Peer - Didactic	Engagement through learning from peers (discussion groups, family and friends) <-> didactic and structured learning (tools, classroom)
Dim. 3	Media - Experiential	Engagement through the Agri-media <-> learning from experience (on-the-job, advisor)

Figure 5 Within-Cluster Sum of Squares by Number of Clusters

ANOVA confirmed significant differences across clusters on all five CATPCA dimensions, indicating adequate separation for interpretation.

Table 12 Cluster Sizes and Centres for CATPCA Dimensions Across Clusters

	n	Resources - Practices	People - Equipment	Informal - Formal	Peer - Didactic	Media - Experiential
Cluster 1	439	0.26	0.64	0.56	0.24	0.38
Cluster 2	194	-0.19	0.31	-1.13	0.96	-0.68
Cluster 3	213	0.77	-1.38	0.40	-0.15	-0.09
Cluster 4	232	-1.05	-0.21	-0.48	-1.12	-0.07

Note: Values represent cluster centres (mean CATPCA dimension scores). Positive scores indicate preference toward the first-named pole of each dimension; negative scores indicate preference toward the second-named pole.

Figure 6 Cluster Analysis Results

Demographic Associations

Chi-square tests examined whether demographic characteristics were associated with cluster membership. Results are presented in Table 13. Age ($p = 0.002$, Cramér's $V = 0.097$) and Farm Size ($p = 0.010$, Cramér's $V = 0.087$) were statistically significantly associated with cluster membership. However, in both cases the effect sizes were trivial ($V < 0.10$), suggesting these associations reflect small distributional effects rather than substantive demographic differences between clusters. The

remaining demographic variables (gender, farm occupation, farm type) did not significantly differ across clusters.

Table 13 Cluster demographic chi-square results

Variable	χ^2	DF	P-value
Gender	6.925	3	0.074
Age	30.322	12	0.002
Farm Occupation	9.170	6	0.164
Farm Type	25.102	21	0.243
Farm Size	21.603	9	0.010

This finding is noteworthy: cluster membership was determined entirely by differences in safety and engagement preferences rather than by demographic characteristics. Based on the data available to us, farmers cannot be differentiated into these groups based on their age, gender, occupation, farm type, or farm size. Instead, the groups reflect genuinely different orientations toward safety priorities and learning preferences that cut across demographic categories.

Cluster Interpretation

The four clusters represent distinct farmer profiles characterised by different combinations of safety priorities and engagement preferences. The first two groups are primarily distinguished by their preferences for engagement at different socioecological levels, while the latter two groups are distinguished by their different approaches to risk management.

Cluster 1: Interpersonal Learners (40.7%, n = 439)

The largest group in the sample, Interpersonal Learners show moderate preferences for the people-focused end of the People—Equipment dimension (+0.64) and informal learning channels (+0.56 on Informal—Formal). They also show a slight preference for media-based engagement (+0.38 on Media—Experiential). This group prioritises safety through managing social connections with others on the farm and prefers informal, relationship-based learning over formal organisational engagement. They are the only group showing a positive score on Media—Experiential, suggesting openness to agri-media as an information source.

Interpersonal Learners are defined by their reliance on personal social networks for safety knowledge, prioritising personal networks over organisational and formalised farm safety structures. This profile aligns with patterns observed in farmer help-seeking behaviour more broadly, where farmers often rely on close social networks for advice across various domains including mental health (Malone et al., 2025). From a Diffusion of Innovation perspective, this group might be characterised as 'late adopters'; however, through our Socioecological Model framework, we recognise them as highly connected and information-seeking—but through channels that educational organisations rarely utilise systematically.

Cluster 2: Organisational Learners (17.9%, n = 194)

The smallest group, Organisational Learners show a distinctive profile combining strong preferences for formal engagement channels (-1.13 on Informal—Formal), peer-based learning (+0.96 on Peer—Didactic), and experiential application (-0.68 on Media—Experiential). Their safety priority scores are relatively neutral, suggesting openness to various safety approaches rather than strong preferences for specific issues.

This profile indicates farmers who seek learning delivered through organisational channels: they want formal, structured settings (such as classrooms or organised discussion groups) where knowledge is developed collaboratively with peers and then applied experientially through on-the-job practice. They value both the structure that organisations provide and the peer networks that organisations facilitate,

viewing organisations as platforms for connecting with other farmers rather than solely as sources of top-down information.

Organisational Learners represent the group that advisory and extension services may perceive as 'good' or highly engaged farmers (Vanclay, 2011). From a Diffusion of Innovation perspective, they might be classified as early adopters due to their connection to formal educational organisations. However, our findings highlight that while these farmers are well-served by existing systems, they represent less than one-fifth of the farming population.

Cluster 3: Risk Preventers (19.8%, n = 213)

Risk Preventers show the most distinctive safety priority profile, with strong preferences for resources (+0.77 on Resources—Practices) and equipment (-1.38 on People—Equipment). Their engagement preference scores cluster near zero across all three Q2 dimensions, indicating no strong preferences for particular learning approaches.

This group focuses on preventive measures to ensure safety, prioritising adequate financial resources, labour availability, and equipment quality over behavioural practices or interpersonal support. They represent a traditional Hierarchy of Controls orientation, emphasising engineering solutions and resource acquisition. Their near-neutral engagement scores present a different challenge for farm safety organisations than Interpersonal Learners: while the latter prefer informal channels, Risk Preventers have no strong channel preference at all, suggesting their engagement approach varies individually and may depend on what specific resource or equipment need they are addressing.

Cluster 4: Knowledge First (21.5%, n = 232)

Knowledge First farmers show strong preferences for practices over resources (-1.05 on Resources—Practices) and didactic over peer-based learning (-1.12 on Peer—Didactic), with a moderate preference for formal channels (-0.48 on Informal—Formal). Their People—Equipment score is near neutral (-0.21).

This profile indicates farmers who prioritise awareness, training, and protective behaviours as their approach to safety, and prefer acquiring this knowledge through structured, didactic learning environments. They strongly favour formal educational approaches—such as classroom-based training that incorporates systematic risk assessment principles—over peer-based discussion. This group values expertise and structured knowledge transfer, preferring to learn from authoritative sources rather than through informal peer exchange.

Together with Risk Preventers, Knowledge First farmers represent the higher levels of the adapted Hierarchy of Controls framework used in this study: Risk Preventers prioritise engineering and resource solutions, while Knowledge First farmers prioritise awareness and capacity-building. However, their engagement preferences differ markedly—Risk Preventers show no strong engagement preferences, while Knowledge First farmers clearly prefer formal, didactic approaches.

3.7 Applying the Farmer Profiles to European Safety Systems

The four farmer profiles identified through cluster analysis—Interpersonal Learners, Organisational Learners, Risk Preventers, and Knowledge First farmers—provide a framework for evaluating current national safety systems and the extent to which they serve different segments of the farming population. Following the completion of the analysis that identified the four clusters of farmers presented above, CoPs in eight countries (Poland, Germany, Finland, Slovenia, Ireland, Lithuania, Romania, and France) provided a rapid assessment of safety support systems against these profiles to identify strengths, gaps, and opportunities for improvement. This section synthesises their findings thematically, drawing out cross-European patterns and highlighting where specific countries offer instructive examples.

3.7.1 Supporting Interpersonal Learners

Interpersonal Learners comprise the largest segment of our sample (40.7%) yet emerge as the most underserved group across European safety systems. These farmers prioritise personal social networks for safety knowledge and prefer informal, relationship-based learning over formal organisational engagement. They show openness to agri-media as an information source but are largely disconnected from structured safety programmes.

Current provision across Europe

Existing supports for this group are characterised by sporadic, unsystematic initiatives rather than comprehensive programmes. Across the participating countries, Interpersonal Learners are primarily reached through:

- **Agricultural media content:** Safety information published in online magazines, newspapers, and social media platforms, typically produced by social insurance agencies (Poland, Germany), labour inspectorates (Poland, Slovenia, Ireland), or research organisations (Ireland). However, this content is produced irregularly, and its effectiveness remains largely unevaluated.
- **Agricultural events:** Safety awareness activities at fairs, exhibitions, and field demonstrations provide opportunities for informal peer exchange (Poland, Germany, Slovenia, Ireland). These events allow farmers to meet and share experiences, but safety messaging is often secondary to other purposes.
- **On-farm advisor visits:** In some countries, advisors conduct farm visits that may address safety issues informally (Poland, France). However, these are typically not systematic safety-focused interventions.

Gaps and challenges

No participating country reported systematic, evaluated programmes specifically designed to reach farmers through their informal social networks. The channels this group prefers—family conversations, peer exchange, community-based learning—receive minimal institutional investment. Several CoPs acknowledged that while agri-media content is produced, there is no evidence base regarding whether it changes farmer behaviour or reaches the intended audience.

France noted that farmers in this group "mainly get their OSH information from discussing with their neighbours, family and friends in informal meetings, or witnessing significant events (such as severe farming accidents), or learning at meetings on topics other than occupational health and safety." This observation highlights both the reality of how Interpersonal Learners currently access safety information and the missed opportunity to systematically leverage these channels.

Promising approaches

Despite the general gap, several examples suggest potential pathways:

- **Community-embedded initiatives:** Ireland reported pilot initiatives seeking to develop "communities of safe farm practice," though these are new and not yet evaluated. Slovenia's 'Slovenian Rural Youth Association' peer networks aim to build safe farm communities, though formal impact assessment is limited.
- **Leveraging existing social structures:** Poland's "farmers' circles" (though few in number) and local support groups provide models for community-based safety engagement. Finland's Leader-funding approach, which supports grassroots local development through bottom-up ideation, offers a structural model for community-embedded initiatives.
- **Integrating safety into broader programming:** France suggested that working OSH topics into general farming meetings—rather than standalone safety events—could gradually reach farmers who engage informally. This "indirect communication" approach recognises that Interpersonal Learners may be more receptive to safety messages embedded in contexts they already value.

3.7.2 Supporting Organisational Learners

Organisational Learners represent the smallest segment (17.9%) but are the most comprehensively served across European safety systems. These farmers actively engage with a number of organisations, value both formal structure and peer interaction, and seek experiential application of knowledge. They value complete learning support, i.e. organised training, peer discussion, and practical application.

Current provision across Europe

This group benefits from extensive and varied learning opportunities delivered through established institutional infrastructure:

- **Expert-facilitated discussion groups:** Agricultural advisory services across Europe provide structured peer-to-peer learning forums. Ireland's Teagasc operates discussion groups connecting farmers with experts; Germany's Technical Supervisory Service (TSS) accompanies farmer groups and participates in specialist courses; Slovenia's Agricultural Advisory Service (JSKS) at the Chamber of Agriculture (KGZS) delivers expert-facilitated training; Lithuania's Agricultural Advisory Service (LAAS) provides both face-to-face and e-learning services; and France's MSA prevention officers participate in thematic farmer meetings.
- **Workshops, courses, and practical demonstrations:** Poland's Agricultural Social Insurance Fund (ASIF) and State Labour Inspection organise workshops, competitions, and safe work demonstrations. Germany's SVLFG offers events as part of continuing education, including programmes at universities and vocational schools. Finland's advisory services and expert organisations coordinate benchmarking groups with deeper peer learning opportunities.
- **Structured educational programmes:** Agricultural colleges and vocational training institutions serve this group through formal curricula that combine classroom instruction with practical application (Ireland, Germany, Finland, Slovenia, Lithuania, Poland).

Why this group is well-served

The alignment between Organisational Learners' preferences and existing institutional provision is not coincidental. Advisory and extension services have historically evolved to meet the needs of farmers who actively engage with them (Vanclay, 2011). As noted in the literature, this group matches what advisory services may perceive as "good" or highly engaged farmers. The current system reflects decades of institutional learning about how to serve farmers who seek out formal support.

Considerations

While Organisational Learners are well-served, they represent less than one-fifth of the farming population. The comprehensiveness of support for this group highlights, by contrast, the challenges in reaching farmers with different preferences. Furthermore, the sustainability of current provision depends on continued public funding for advisory services—a consideration noted by several CoPs. Finland's model, which coordinates multiple discussion group organisations under a registered brand ("Discussion Group—from entrepreneur to entrepreneur"), demonstrates how peer learning can be systematised while maintaining farmer-to-farmer authenticity. Germany's combination of legally enshrined safety support with free, tailored training programmes illustrates how comprehensive social insurance systems can serve this group effectively.

3.7.3 Supporting Risk Preventers

Risk Preventers (19.8%) prioritise material resources, equipment quality, and engineering solutions to address farm safety. They show no strong preference for any particular engagement approach, meaning their learning pathway varies individually depending on the specific resource or equipment need they are addressing.

Current provision across Europe

Support for this group is concentrated in policy-level funding mechanisms rather than direct engagement programmes:

- **CAP and national funding for farm modernisation:** Across all participating countries, farmers can access EU Common Agricultural Policy funding and national programmes for investments in machinery, equipment, and infrastructure that indirectly improve safety. Poland's Agency for Restructuring and Modernization of Agriculture, Lithuania's National Paying Agency, Romania's National Agency for Financing Rural Development, and Ireland's Department of Agriculture, Food and the Marine all administer such schemes. These enable farmers to upgrade to safer, more ergonomic machinery and improve farm infrastructure.
- **Targeted equipment programmes:** Some countries offer specific safety-focused equipment support. Poland's ASIF runs a PTO shaft guard replacement programme, providing new guards to replace worn or faulty ones. Germany's SVLFG operates a premium system that directly incentivises investment in preventive safety measures, complemented by free individual consultation.
- **Technical inspection and compliance:** Slovenia's Ministry of Infrastructure and police conduct tractor inspections, whilst the Labour Inspectorate promotes safer machinery use through campaigns and enforcement.

Gaps and challenges

While funding mechanisms exist, several limitations affect Risk Preventers:

- **Indirect rather than direct support:** Most provision addresses safety indirectly through general farm modernisation rather than targeting safety improvements specifically. Romania noted that "the impact is very limited due to the reduced number of programs and the self-selection bias in terms of resources and expertise needed for implementing these types of projects."
- **Labour shortages unaddressed:** Risk Preventers prioritise having adequate help on the farm, yet few countries offer systematic support for farm labour. Finland stands out with Europe's most comprehensive farmer relief scheme, enabling farmers to take time for training, recovery, or implementing safety improvements. Ireland and Slovenia both noted the absence of equivalent schemes as a significant gap.
- **No engagement pathway:** Because Risk Preventers lack strong engagement preferences, they are difficult to reach through standard communication channels. Their focus on equipment and resources means they may engage with machinery dealers, contractors, or agricultural suppliers rather than safety-specific organisations—yet these commercial channels are rarely integrated into safety support systems.

Promising approaches

- **Social insurance premium incentives:** Germany's model, where safety investments reduce insurance premiums, directly aligns with Risk Preventers' resource-focused orientation. The premium system creates a financial incentive for safety investment that speaks to some of this group's priorities.
- **Facilitated practical support:** France reported women farmers' groups working with Chamber of Agriculture or Civam facilitators on ergonomics, workspace layout, and equipment improvements. This model—practical, equipment-focused, but facilitated rather than self-directed—may bridge Risk Preventers' equipment focus with structured support.
- **Replacement worker systems:** Finland's farmer holiday and stand-in scheme directly addresses the time and labour constraints that prevent Risk Preventers from implementing safety improvements. Broader adoption of similar schemes could significantly enhance support for this group.

3.7.4 Supporting Knowledge First Farmers

Knowledge First farmers (21.5%) prioritise awareness, training, and protective behaviours, preferring to acquire safety knowledge through structured, didactic learning environments. They favour formal educational approaches and expert-delivered content over peer-based discussion.

Current provision across Europe

This group is systematically served through formal educational institutions and structured training programmes:

- **Agricultural education systems:** Universities, agricultural colleges, and vocational schools across Europe provide classroom-based safety education. Poland noted training available through ASIF, State Labour Inspection, and scientific institutions; Germany highlighted occupational safety content in vocational training; Lithuania's Vytautas Magnus University Agriculture Academy offers formal education, conferences, and risk-assessment training; Finland emphasised that farmers have access to good education and are highly educated as a population.
- **Structured professional development:** Germany's SVLFG ILIAS self-learning platform provides a structured digital learning environment supporting didactic knowledge acquisition. Slovenia's regulated tractor and tool safety modules and JSKS/KGZS seminars offer consistent, classroom-based education.
- **Risk assessment tools and frameworks:** Lithuania promotes the OiRA (Online Interactive Risk Assessment) tool with versions tailored to agricultural settings. France noted that farmers employing workers engage with structured risk assessment through the legally required DUERP (occupational risk assessment document), supported by MSA prevention officers.

Gaps and challenges

- **Variable integration of safety in curricula:** While educational institutions exist across Europe, the extent to which occupational safety is integrated into agricultural curricula varies considerably. Germany noted that "occupational health and safety is not adequately addressed in vocational training in the green sector" and that "teaching content refers to legally required measures and does not take into account the framework conditions in agriculture." Poland and Romania both identified the need for better integration of safety into formal agricultural education.
- **Accessibility constraints:** Not all Knowledge First farmers can access classroom-based learning due to geographic, time, or financial constraints. Finland noted that "not all farmers can attend classroom-based courses" and that farm visits and presentations are organised to reach farmers in dispersed areas.
- **Knowledge-practice gap:** Slovenia observed that while "knowledge gains are reliable" from structured educational approaches, "routine practice lags without experiential components and cues." This suggests that didactic learning alone may be insufficient—Knowledge First farmers may benefit from approaches that bridge structured knowledge acquisition with practical application prompts.

Promising approaches

- **Comprehensive social insurance education programmes:** Germany's free training programme tailored specifically to farmers, delivered through the SVLFG, demonstrates how social insurance systems can provide accessible, structured learning. The combination of legally enshrined safety support with tailored educational delivery serves some of the needs of Knowledge First farmers.
- **Blended learning models:** Finland's approach of supplementing classroom courses with farm visits and practical presentations addresses accessibility while maintaining the structured, expert-delivered content this group prefers.

- **Embedding safety in broader professional development:** Romania noted that improved OSH awareness often comes "indirectly and embedded in broader acquisition of knowledge about the work in agriculture" through agricultural high school and university programmes. While this indirect approach has limitations, it ensures some safety content reaches farmers through channels they already engage with.

3.7.5 Cross-Cutting Observations

Several patterns emerge from this thematic analysis that cut across individual farmer profiles:

The role of social insurance systems. Countries with comprehensive agricultural social insurance systems—notably Germany (SVLFG), France (MSA), Poland (ASIF), and Finland (Mela)—demonstrate capacity to serve multiple farmer profiles through coordinated provision. These systems combine funding mechanisms (serving Risk Preventers), educational programmes (serving Knowledge First farmers), facilitated group learning (serving Organisational Learners), and outreach activities (potentially reaching Interpersonal Learners). The institutional integration enables differentiated approaches within a coherent framework. It is important to stress that a comprehensive agricultural social insurance system is not a prerequisite to serving the needs of different groups of farmers.

The potential of advisory services. Agricultural advisory services provide the backbone of support for Organisational Learners across Europe, but their reach to other profiles is limited. Extending advisory capacity to serve Interpersonal Learners (through community-embedded approaches) or Risk Preventers (through practical equipment-focused support) would require deliberate expansion beyond traditional modes of operation.

The persistent challenge of informal channels. Despite Interpersonal Learners comprising the largest farmer segment, no country reported systematic approaches in reaching farmers through informal social networks. This represents the most significant gap in current European provision and the area requiring greatest innovation, e.g. working with social medial influencers.

Evaluation deficits. Across all profiles and countries, CoPs consistently noted limited evaluation of existing programmes' effectiveness. Even well-established approaches serving Organisational Learners lack robust evidence of behaviour change outcomes. For newer or more sporadic initiatives targeting other profiles, evaluation is largely absent. Building an evidence base for what works—and for whom—emerges as a priority across the European agricultural safety system.

4. General Conclusions

This deliverable presents findings from two complementary studies examining farm safety and health across 11 European countries. Together, they provide an evidence base for understanding both what needs to be addressed and how different farming populations can be effectively engaged.

4.1 Synthesis of Findings

4.1.1 Study Contributions

Study 1 (Priority Needs Register) synthesised expert and stakeholder knowledge through systematic consultation with Communities of Practice in 11 countries. This process identified 229 specific safety and health hazards, issues, challenges, and needs, revealing not only the immediate risks farmers face but also the underpinning constructs—systemic social, cultural, and economic factors—that shape safety outcomes. Critically, the analysis demonstrated that addressing farm safety requires coordinated action across multiple actor groups: farmers and citizens, public organisations, research and education institutions, and private sector bodies.

Study 2 (Survey and Cluster Analysis) captured farmer perspectives directly, surveying 1,078 farmers, farmworkers, family members, and agricultural students across the same 11 countries. The analysis identified farmers' safety priorities and, through cluster analysis, revealed four distinct farmer profiles distinguished by their engagement preferences rather than demographic characteristics. These findings challenge assumptions that farmers can be effectively reached through uniform approaches and provides an evidence base for diversifying engagement strategies.

4.1.2 Points of Convergence

The two studies converge on several fundamental points, strengthening confidence in the findings through triangulation from expert and end-user perspectives.

Safety culture as foundational challenge. Study 1 identified "low management commitment on safety / lack of safety culture on farms" as the most frequently cited underpinning construct, mentioned by all 11 CoPs. Study 2's finding that "awareness of health and safety risks" was farmers' top-ranked safety priority confirms that farmers themselves recognise awareness and culture as foundational. Both studies point toward the same conclusion: technical solutions and equipment improvements, while necessary, are insufficient without attention to the cultural and awareness dimensions of farm safety.

Multi-actor and multi-level responses required. The Priority Needs Register organised needs across four stakeholder groups, demonstrating that no single actor can address farm safety challenges alone. Study 2's application of the Socioecological Model to engagement preferences similarly revealed that farmers operate within multiple levels—individual, interpersonal, organisational, community, and policy—and effective engagement must work across these levels. The convergence validates the SafeHabitus project's multi-actor approach and supports recommendations for coordinated action rather than isolated interventions.

Labour constraints and time poverty. Study 1 identified "farmers forced to work ill and injured" and labour shortages as critical underpinning constructs, with farmers unable to take time for training, health appointments, or implementing safety improvements. Study 2's Risk Preventers profile (20% of sample) prioritised "help on the farm or time to get everything done" alongside equipment and infrastructure solutions. Both studies identify the same constraint: farmers know what they need to do but lack the time and labour resources to do it. This convergence supports recommendations for replacement worker schemes and direct labour support alongside funding for equipment.

Equipment and infrastructure matter. Study 1 documented extensive needs related to machinery safety, livestock handling facilities, and farm infrastructure. Study 2 found "safe machinery or equipment" as farmers' second-highest safety priority, and Risk Preventers specifically prioritised material resources and engineering solutions. The alignment confirms that higher levels of the Hierarchy of Controls—elimination and substitution of hazards through better equipment and design—remain essential components of farm safety strategy.

Diverse engagement approaches needed. Study 1's analysis of priority needs by stakeholder group revealed multiple pathways for addressing safety challenges, from formal training and education to peer networks and private sector engagement. Study 2 empirically demonstrated this diversity, identifying four distinct farmer profiles with fundamentally different engagement preferences. The convergence provides robust evidence that one-size-fits-all approaches to farm safety engagement will inevitably fail to reach substantial portions of the farming population.

4.1.3 Points of Tension and Complementarity

The two studies also reveal productive tensions—areas where expert-identified needs differ from farmer-expressed priorities. These tensions are analytically valuable, indicating where awareness-raising, system reform, or alternative engagement strategies may be needed.

Interpersonal support: expert emphasis versus farmer ambivalence. Study 1 strongly emphasised the role of family, social networks, and interpersonal relationships in farm safety, identifying social isolation and lack of support networks as critical challenges. However, Study 2 found that "talking with family and friends" ranked lowest among farmers' engagement preferences overall. This apparent tension is resolved by the cluster analysis: Interpersonal Learners (40% of sample) do prioritise informal, relationship-based learning, but other farmer profiles actively avoid it. The implication is that interpersonal approaches are essential for reaching a large segment of farmers but should not be assumed universal. Experts are correct that interpersonal dimensions matter; the refinement is understanding for whom they matter most.

Risk assessment tools: promoted but not preferred. Farm safety policy and practice across Europe has invested substantially in risk assessment tools, checklists, and structured assessment processes. Study 2 found these ranked lowest among farmers' engagement preferences alongside talking with family. Yet Study 1's Priority Needs Register identified risk identification and management as a critical need across multiple countries. This tension suggests that while risk assessment remains important, current tool-based approaches may not align with how most farmers prefer to engage with safety information. The exception is Knowledge First farmers (22% of sample), who do show relative preference for structured, didactic approaches including tools. For other profiles, risk assessment content may need to be delivered through different channels—peer discussion, advisor conversations, or practical demonstration rather than self-administered tools.

Training and formal education: supply versus demand alignment. Study 1 identified OSH education gaps as a critical underpinning construct, with multiple CoPs noting inadequate safety content in agricultural education and training. Study 2 found that classroom-based training ranked among farmers' top engagement preferences—but this preference was concentrated among Organisational Learners (18%) and Knowledge First farmers (22%). The remaining 60% of farmers showed lower enthusiasm for formal training approaches. This suggests that while expanding OSH content in agricultural education is appropriate (and will reach those who engage with formal education), it will not reach the majority of farmers. Complementary informal approaches are needed.

Systemic factors: visible to experts, less salient to farmers. Study 1's most significant contribution may be its identification of underpinning constructs—systemic factors including safety culture, stress

and workload, generational renewal challenges, and regulatory gaps. These structural factors were consistently identified by expert stakeholders across all 11 countries. Study 2's farmer survey, by design focused on immediate priorities and preferences, captured these factors less directly. Farmers prioritised awareness and equipment—more proximate concerns—over systemic issues like "support from family, friends, and important others" or "training from organisations." This is not a contradiction but a difference in perspective: farmers experience the consequences of systemic factors (time pressure, stress, inadequate support) without necessarily framing them as systemic. The implication for policy is that addressing underpinning constructs requires action at policy and institutional levels, not merely responding to farmer-expressed preferences.

4.1.4 Implications of the Synthesis

Three overarching implications emerge from synthesising both studies.

First, the evidence base is robust. Where expert-identified needs and farmer-expressed priorities converge—on safety culture, multi-actor responses, labour constraints, equipment needs, and engagement diversity—we can be confident these represent genuine priorities for European farm safety policy. The triangulation from different methodological approaches and different respondent groups strengthens the foundation for recommendations.

Second, farmer heterogeneity is fundamental. The identification of four distinct farmer profiles, each with different engagement preferences, is perhaps the most significant finding for implementation. It explains why previous interventions may have shown limited effectiveness: approaches designed for Organisational Learners (the farmers most visible to advisory services) systematically miss Interpersonal Learners (the largest group). Effective farm safety systems must offer multiple pathways.

Third, structural change requires policy action. The underpinning constructs identified in Study 1—safety culture, labour constraints, generational challenges, regulatory gaps—cannot be addressed through farmer-level interventions alone. They require coordinated action at EU and Member State levels, involving agricultural policy, employment policy, health policy, and education policy. The recommendations that follow are structured to address this multi-level, multi-actor challenge.

4.2 Policy and Practice Recommendations

The findings from Studies 1 and 2 points toward specific policy reforms and practice changes that can address the systemic factors affecting European farmers' health and safety. The Priority Needs Register demonstrates that farm safety challenges arise from interconnected causes requiring multi-actor responses, while the farmer profiles reveal that current engagement approaches systematically underserve substantial portions of the farming population.

To accommodate different policy cycles and governance structures, the recommendations below are organised according to their implementation pathway and timeline:

- **Tier 1 recommendations** can be implemented within the current CAP programming period (2023-2027) through existing governance mechanisms
- **Tier 2 recommendations** align with specific elements of the proposed Post-2027 CAP framework (2028-2034) and should be considered during the current legislative negotiation process
- **Tier 3 recommendations** require longer-term systemic change involving coordination beyond agricultural policy alone

This is followed by recommendations for Member States that can be implemented through national policy frameworks.

4.2.1 Tier 1: Immediate Opportunities (2023-2027)

These recommendations can be implemented within existing frameworks without new legislation.

A.1 Integration of OSH into Farm Advisory Services

Findings addressed: Study 1 (underpinning constructs on safety culture and OSH education gaps); Study 2 (Knowledge First and Organisational Learners)

Recommendation: Member States should integrate occupational safety and health as a standard component of Farm Advisory Services (FAS), drawing on the four farmer profiles identified in this research to tailor engagement approaches to different learning preferences.

Implementation pathway: This can be implemented as guidance to advisory bodies without Strategic Plan amendment. The current CAP Strategic Plans Regulation requires FAS to cover economic, environmental and social dimensions, providing sufficient scope for OSH integration.

Responsible bodies: Member State ministries, national FAS providers, DG AGRI (guidance)

A.2 Farm Safety Communities of Practice

Findings addressed: Study 1 (multi-actor collaboration needs); Study 2 (Interpersonal Learners)

Recommendation: Member States should utilise existing LEADER funding and EIP-AGRI mechanisms to establish or strengthen Farm Safety Communities of Practice, building on the model demonstrated by the SafeHabitus project and national examples such as the Irish Farm Safety Partnership.

Implementation pathway: LEADER Local Action Groups can include farm safety as a priority theme within existing Local Development Strategies. EIP-AGRI Operational Groups can be established to address specific safety challenges. No Strategic Plan amendment is required where these activities fall within existing intervention scope.

Responsible bodies: Member State managing authorities, LEADER Local Action Groups, national rural networks

A.3 Pilot Programmes for Interpersonal Learners

Findings addressed: Study 2 (Interpersonal Learners comprising 40% of sample but currently underserved across some countries)

Recommendation: Member States should pilot community-embedded safety initiatives that reach farmers through informal social networks, integrating safety messaging into existing farmer-to-farmer knowledge exchange mechanisms such as discussion groups, farm walks, and peer mentoring programmes.

Implementation pathway: Integration with existing knowledge transfer programmes, e.g. EIP-AGRI.

Responsible bodies: National advisory services, farm organisations, agricultural education bodies

4.2.2 Tier 2: Post-2027 CAP Integration (2028-2034)

These recommendations align with specific elements of the proposed Post-2027 CAP framework (COM (2025) 560) and should be considered during the current legislative negotiation process.

B.1 Farm Relief Services for Safety Implementation

Findings addressed: Study 1 (farmers working while ill/injured, labour shortages as underpinning construct); Study 2 (Risk Preventers needing time for safety improvements)

Recommendation: Member States should utilise the new farm relief services provision to enable farmers to attend safety training, implement safety improvements, and recover from injuries without compromising farm operations. Relief services should be designed to provide both planned coverage (for training, rest, family responsibilities) and emergency coverage following farm accidents.

Rationale: Both studies demonstrate that time poverty and labour constraints prevent farmers from implementing safety improvements. The Priority Needs Register identified "farmers forced to work ill and injured" as a critical underpinning construct across multiple countries. The proposed Article 17

(Farm relief services) provides a mechanism to address this; Finland's comprehensive replacement worker scheme demonstrates one implementation approach.

Responsible bodies: Member State ministries, DG AGRI (guidance in CAP national recommendations)

B.2 Safety Integration in Generational Renewal Strategy

Findings addressed: Study 1 (sector attractiveness, generation gap as underpinning construct); Study 2 (agricultural students included in sample)

Recommendation: Member States should include occupational safety and health as an explicit element of the mandatory Generational Renewal Strategy, recognising that dangerous working conditions and high injury rates deter young people from entering agriculture and contribute to succession failures.

Rationale: The Priority Needs Register identified the ageing farming population and lack of young people entering agriculture as a critical challenge across several countries. The proposed Article 15 requires Member States to establish a Generational Renewal Strategy including "identification of entry barriers for young farmers"; OSH risks constitute a significant but often unacknowledged barrier.

Responsible bodies: Member State ministries, DG AGRI (CAP national recommendations and Strategy assessment criteria)

B.3 Young Farmer Starter Pack—Safety Component

Findings addressed: Study 1 (OSH education gaps); Study 2 (farmer profiles apply to new entrants)

Recommendation: The Starter Pack for young farmers should explicitly include safety training and advisory support tailored to young farmers' engagement preferences. Access to advisory services should cover OSH alongside business management, with particular attention to the transition period when young farmers are establishing new practices and routines.

Responsible bodies: Member State ministries, agricultural education institutions, advisory services

B.4 Investment Support Prioritising Safety Infrastructure

Findings addressed: Study 1 (equipment and infrastructure needs); Study 2 (Risk Preventers prioritising material resources and engineering solutions)

Recommendation: Member States should prioritise investment support for infrastructure and technologies that demonstrably reduce occupational safety risks, with particular attention to small and medium farms where resources for safety improvements are most constrained. Priority investments identified in this research include livestock handling facilities, machinery safety features, and farm layout improvements that reduce manual handling and injury risk.

Rationale: Risk Preventers (20% of sample) prioritise equipment and infrastructure solutions but lack strong engagement preferences, suggesting that they are best reached through investment mechanisms rather than educational programmes. The proposed Article 13 (Support for investments) provides the mechanism to deliver these supports.

Responsible bodies: Member State ministries, paying agencies

B.5 Diverse Engagement Approaches in AKIS

Findings addressed: Study 2 (four farmer profiles requiring different engagement approaches)

Recommendation: The Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation System (AKIS) description required in National Plans should include explicit consideration of how advisory services and knowledge transfer will reach farmers with different learning preferences. This should encompass formal channels (classroom training, structured advisory services) for Organisational Learners and Knowledge First farmers, alongside informal channels (peer networks, community-embedded approaches) for Interpersonal Learners.

Rationale: Current AKIS provision across Europe primarily serves Organisational Learners and Knowledge First farmers through formal advisory and educational structures. The 40% of farmers identified as Interpersonal Learners require different approaches that are currently sporadic and unevaluated.

Responsible bodies: Member State ministries, national advisory services, DG AGRI (AKIS assessment criteria)

B.6 LEADER for Community-Based Safety Initiatives

Findings addressed: Study 2 (Interpersonal Learners currently underserved); Study 1 (social isolation as underpinning construct)

Recommendation: Member States should ensure LEADER local development strategies can support community-based farm safety initiatives, particularly in rural areas with specific disadvantages where formal advisory services are limited and social isolation compounds safety risks.

Responsible bodies: LEADER Local Action Groups, Member State managing authorities

B.7 EIP-AGRI Focus on Farm Safety Innovation

Findings addressed: Study 1 (multi-actor collaboration needs); Study 2 (Organisational Learners)

Recommendation: The Commission should encourage EIP-AGRI Operational Groups addressing farm safety challenges, with particular focus on developing innovative approaches to reach underserved farmer populations and supporting farm households affected by injury. Results should be disseminated through the EU CAP Network to enable cross-border learning.

Responsible bodies: DG AGRI, EIP-AGRI Service Point, national rural networks

4.2.3 Tier 3: Vision for Integrated Farm Safety Support

These recommendations require longer-term systemic change involving coordination beyond agricultural policy alone.

C.1 Evaluation of National Safety Service Portfolios

Findings addressed: Study 2 (four farmer profiles with varying service coverage across Member States)

Recommendation: Through Horizon Europe and national research initiatives, Member States should evaluate their current farm safety service portfolios against the four farmer profiles identified in this research, identify underserved groups, and develop differentiated engagement strategies. This evaluation should assess current provision for Interpersonal Learners, Organisational Learners, Risk Preventers, and Knowledge First farmers, identifying gaps and opportunities for service development. This knowledge will inform the guidance to advisory bodies on reaching farmers who do not engage with formal services (See recommendation B.5, Diverse Engagement Approaches in AKIS).

Responsible bodies: DG RTD, national research funding bodies, Member State ministries

C.2 Research on Consequences of Farm Injuries

Findings addressed: Study 1 (consequences flowing upward through socioecological levels); Study 2 (implications for household and community)

Recommendation: The European Commission should support research examining the medium and long-term consequences of farm injuries on farmers, farm households, rural communities, and the agricultural sector. This should include longitudinal studies tracking injured farmers and their households, and investigation of how injuries create conditions for subsequent injuries through intensification of labour burden on remaining household members. These studies should also consider the implications of serious injuries for the social and economic viability of farming.

Responsible bodies: DG RTD, DG AGRI, national research funding bodies

C.3 OSH Coverage for Self-Employed Farmers

Findings addressed: Study 1 (underpinning constructs showing self-employed farmers lack institutional protection)

Recommendation: While recognising the principle of self-employment, consideration should be given to how occupational safety and health protections can be extended or adapted for self-employed farmers. This may involve voluntary frameworks, social conditionality mechanisms, or adaptation of existing OSH directive provisions to agricultural contexts.

Limitation noted: Current social conditionality provisions in the Post-2027 CAP address employer obligations for hired workers but do not regulate self-employed farmers' own working conditions. Extending OSH coverage to self-employed farmers requires action beyond CAP alone, involving coordination between DG AGRI, DG EMPL, and national authorities.

Responsible bodies: European Commission (DG AGRI, DG EMPL), Member State ministries

4.2.4 Recommendations for Member States

The following recommendations can be implemented through national policy frameworks, independent of CAP programming cycles.

For National and Regional Governments

Member States should:

- Evaluate current farm safety engagement services against the four farmer profiles identified in this research to identify underserved populations and develop targeted strategies
- Ensure agricultural OSH is included within the remit of national advisory services and receives adequate funding for both formal and informal engagement approaches
- Consider establishing or expanding replacement worker schemes that enable farmers to take time for training, health appointments, and recovery from injury
- Integrate OSH content into agricultural education at all levels, from vocational training through university programmes

For Agricultural Advisory and Extension Services

Advisory services should:

- Diversify engagement methods beyond classroom-based and formal advisory approaches to reach Interpersonal Learners through peer networks, demonstration events, and community-embedded initiatives
- Train advisors to recognise different farmer learning preferences and adapt their engagement approaches accordingly
- Integrate OSH messaging into routine advisory contacts on other topics (farm management, environmental compliance, animal health) rather than treating safety as a separate domain

For Agricultural Education Institutions

Educational institutions should:

- Embed OSH as a core competency throughout agricultural curricula rather than a separate compliance requirement
- Develop training materials and approaches tailored to different learning preferences, recognising that future farmers will also exhibit the diversity of profiles identified in this research
- Support continuing professional development for advisors and trainers on farm safety engagement

For Farm Organisations and Social Partners

Farm organisations should:

- Support peer-to-peer safety knowledge exchange through existing networks and discussion group structures
- Advocate for adequate resourcing of farm safety services within national policy frameworks
- Document and share effective practices for community-embedded safety initiatives

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Annex 1 - Table of Communities of Practice (COP) network focus and priority register in each country.

Country and focus	Priority	Priority	Priority	Priority	Priority
Estonia: focus in cattle and machinery safety guidelines	Safe animal handling: Optimising safe animal handling practices, facilities, and human-animal behaviour in Livestock Farming. This includes training, studies, guidelines, information material and practical exercises	Machinery safety: Improving machinery safety including guidelines for safe machinery use, training and trainer training. Also new machinery, safety investments and support needed	Safety risk management: Supporting farm work risk assessment and management; needs for awareness of major risks and consequences, share of good practices, scheduling, rules for safety culture and workforce management on farms	Network development: Networking to improve the farm safety and farm health knowledge and innovation system	Funding for safety development: funding instruments or incentives provided for farmers to do safety improvements
Finland: focus on dairy farm safety and health management	Safety in animal handling: Improve understanding of animal natural behaviour and human-animal relations in livestock farming, support proper use of PPEs in animal handling on farms	Safety culture and attitude in agriculture: Improving safety attitude and culture in agriculture. This includes stakeholder collaboration, farmer safety campaigns, good practices, use of safety guards and PPE training, video contest engaging young farmers to safety etc.	Occupational health and safety services: A systematic approach to supporting the OSH services of farmers; this includes use of Farmer's Work Ability Index Tool, health screening among farmers, safety and health statistical	Mental health and quality of life: Mental health support for farmers (farmer care program), enhancing quality of life of farmers and farm families: The Farmers' holiday and stand-in scheme system	Knowledge, safety education and innovations: Improve knowledge sharing and funding for safety including safety education in agriculture schools, safety training and marketing for farms, increasing knowledge by safety

			monitoring and risk check development on farms		and health research and searching for new safety innovations
France: focus on cattle farm safety and health	Psychosocial risk handling: tackling psychosocial risks and mental health in farming – Is this connected to workload management and stress? However there two kinds of stress, mental and physic...	One health management: Developing one health approach and tools including safety culture, developing and supporting safety risk management on farms: using Occupational Risk Assessment document, animal handling education, facilities and tools for safety	Safety knowledge development: Raising safety knowledge and awareness among farmers, organizing events and campaigns, developing advisory network, safety orientation for farmers about new machines, training of machinery handling skills	Improving farm ergonomics: Reducing and managing musculoskeletal injuries in farming, farm building safety checks, functions, ergonomic, facilities and handling tools	Farm organisation/ management: Improve scheduling and farm worker management. An overview of initiatives supporting farmers and farm workers. Including overcoming the workload challenge among farmers and the use of Work assessment method (WAM)

<p>Germany: focus of occupational health and safety in the green sector</p>	<p>Safety education: Develop safety and health education, competence training and advisory services, skill documents and safety management certifications (transparent and simply operational)</p>	<p>Safety motivation: Supporting motivation of safety culture by incentives, legal enforcement of 'red' lines (focal points of accidents. Promotion of the sector through the involvement of all economic stakeholders (dealers, associations, etc.) to develop a willingness to work safely in agriculture.</p>	<p>Safe machinery use: Safe machinery use, maintenance and advisory services, setting the minimum safety standards following EU machinery regulation, old machinery use standard, improving safety of tractors and machinery, self-efficient seat belt systems, AI camera warning systems</p>	<p>Safety management: Enhancing safety management on farms, optimising handling practices, facilities, and human-animal relations in livestock farming, tailor-made services</p>	<p>Safety tool development: overview of good practices supporting improvements in farmers' and farm workers' quality of life, stress signs and reporting, develop tools like mobile gas detection, exoskeletons, height work tools development</p>
<p>Ireland: focus working on practical solutions for farm safety and farmer health issues. consider the safety culture in farming, gender, and specific vulnerable populations.</p>	<p>Machinery handling: Safer Tractor Driving: Improving understanding of the risks associated with blind spots, speed and bystander safety. Promoting quad bike safety through helmet use and training. Addressing roll-overs, unguarded machinery, and poor maintenance with operator training, regular upkeep, and retrofitting safety features. Encouraging manufacturers to</p>	<p>Livestock handling: Improving animal handling skills through education, trainer development programmes, peer-to-peer learning. Emphasis on risk awareness, safe handling techniques, and adapting practices for all farmers and ageing farmers in particular.</p>	<p>Work Organisation: Strengthening safety culture and safety management skills by improving workload planning, risk awareness, and decision-making. Enhancing work scheduling, communication skills, and collaboration across different farming styles., support proper use through targeted, ensuring safer approaches to high-risk tasks.</p>	<p>Social sustainability: Strengthen family safety, farmyard safety, and support farm family structures. Raise awareness of farm safety among children. Promote mental health awareness, coping strategies, and stress management. Address isolation and long hours, negative perceptions of farming. Encourage sustainable workloads, sleep and rest.</p>	<p>Services: Tailored services for farmers including farmer health checks, cardiovascular health screenings, etc. Develop advisory support and services, safety tool training for farmers and developing farm safety online tools</p>

	integrate safety measures into machinery design and sales.				
Lithuania: focus ensuring a safe working environment and safety culture on farms	Mental stress handling: Mental and physical well-being connections, can you describe more this development need? Farmers tiredness, poor resources or health, working alone, scheduling, work management etc.?	Stakeholder network collaboration: raising awareness and knowledge in media, safety exhibitions, events, regulations for safety, institutional development, financial support to improve agriculture safety, develop of accident reporting system	Safety education: safety tool training for farmers and trainer training, supporting farmers and farm workers occupational health and safety (by LAAS), making simple safety guidelines for farmers, safety behaviour tips, manual work guidelines, educate about occupational diseases and health hazards	Maintenance on farm: maintenance of machinery, equipment and buildings	Safe animal handling: Optimising Handling Practices, Facilities, and Human-Animal Relations in Livestock Farming

<p>Poland: focus safety and health in Polish individual farming</p>	<p>Systemic solutions for safety education: course to raise of farm safety awareness and knowledge, improving safety culture and management on farms incl. practical safety exercises, use of PTO, safety guard and PPE. Safety education at all levels, also children, youth and schools - inclusion of farm and agricultural safety in school curricula at various levels (mandatory education)</p>	<p>Enhancing farmers' health and well-being: access to health services, periodic health checks, Vision Zero strategy, safety good practices, change management for safer work, safety competitions etc., daycare homes for retired/non-working farmers, rehabilitation holidays for farmers (in sanatoriums)</p>	<p>Modern farming technologies: automation technology, automation risk management, funding systems to support safety investments in agriculture</p>	<p>Farm labour issues: Labour force shortage in agriculture and its implications on the health of those working in the sector, workload management, relief workers - substitution for farmers during illness or possible holidays/rest periods etc..?, generation problem, difficulties in taking over/ enlarging farms</p>	<p>Mental health aid: knowledge about symptoms, risk management, mindfulness and handling techniques, safety trips</p>
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<p>Romania: focus on sheep farm safety and health and connected activities</p>	<p>Improving safety education and training: safety education for those working in agriculture, safety guidelines and examples, digital education, simple safety guidelines and lists, course programs, stakeholders and education collaboration, cooperation between schools, modern teaching technologies, participatory methods, rural schools might organize tailored farm safety programs for parents, future farmers safety training, good practices</p>	<p>Technological upgrading on all farms: enhance safety and health on sheep farms, grants for technology improvement, machinery safety programs, machinery and technology data registering, public facility database for farm technology</p>	<p>Labor management: Increasing the attractiveness of employment in this field by improving the quality of working conditions and how health and safety at work are considered for those in the field. The need for support policies for workforce employment and for assisting young farmers in taking over family farms or starting new farms. Recognition through policies of the risks and difficulties of agricultural work in order to facilitate the development of dedicated solutions</p>	<p>Farmer health and safety support: Supporting occupational health services of farmers and rural communities, health risk screening, ergonomic guidelines for hard weather conditions, weather condition safety management, getting expert feedback, advisory services, local social aid and institutions</p>	<p>Mental health aid: mental health guidelines and risk management, research tools for mental health safety management in agriculture, coping with mental risks and changes among shepherds</p>
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<p>Slovenia: focus on mental health awareness and support: issues, support systems, social networks</p>	<p>Machinery safety: preventing machinery accidents, improving machinery safety on farms, use of seat belts (in vehicles with cabin), using safety guards, technological development on farms (access to well-functioning machinery and tools)</p>	<p>Developing agriculture safety policy: the need for social security of farmers and farm families, farm relief worker system, safety inspections, financial support or funding systems for safety on farms, safety research, safety training and regional support for farmer health services, less bureaucracy, safety culture to notice safety on farms and in policy, media/ public discussion, occupational disease register and monitoring, accident recording data</p>	<p>Psychosocial support for farmers: tackling challenges for the mental health of farmers in Slovenia, listen farmers, social networks, positives in agriculture, handling of mental health factors, psychosocial counselling for farmers, psychosocial support</p>		
<p>Slovakia: focus is on practical solutions to OHS challenges in the agricultural sector</p>	<p>Improving Safety Culture in the Area of Agriculture on National Level: transforming attitudes towards farm safety in Slovakia, cost-effective safety management tools, improving safety management skills, establishing comprehensive</p>	<p>Tailored agriculture education and training: : tailored and focused training on occupational health and safety practices within the agricultural sector, specialized training specifically designed for agricultural settings, safety courses available in agriculture education –</p>	<p>Enhancing Machinery Safety in Agriculture: user-friendly equipment and machinery, proper maintenance and handling of agricultural machinery, safety practices regarding machinery use, development of ergonomic tools,</p>	<p>Enhancing Safety – Optimising Handling Practices and Human Animal Relations in Livestock Farming: standardized protocols and guidelines for safe animal handling practices in agricultural settings, safe animal handling techniques and behaviour</p>	

	regulations and guidelines specifically designed for agricultural settings, dissemination of safety information, stakeholder network collaboration, scheduling, prioritizing, delegating	incorporation of OHS education into formal agricultural curricula at all levels of education, including vocational training programs and university courses, safety protocols, safety practices for routine farm work, practical demonstrations, access for training and education, ergonomic guidelines and education, data on occupational diseases and safety risks	tools for lifting, support for modernization of the machinery, promotion of technological upgrades, machinery maintenance skill programs, comprehensive safety guidelines	management strategies, stress reduction methods for livestock, collaboration with veterinary professionals, infrastructure and equipment upgrades	
Spain: focus on migrant farm worker safety and connected activities, berry and citrus crops	Ergonomics safety education, research and development: preventing impact of heat stress and sun exposure among seasonal migrant farm workers, finding good practices, phytosanitary (pesticide use) management, correct PPE use, PPE use training, clothing, technology development, musculoskeletal disorders/problems?	Work management: safety management, safety culture, supervisor safety training, scheduling and breaks, NGO safety promotion, data collection, safety measures	Mental stress handling: farm worker workshops, psychosocial aid, therapy, proactive worker assistance, communication tools, language mediators, language of labour regulations and safety rules, counselling services, open communication, providing access to health services for migrant farm workers	Accommodation: housing conditions of agricultural migrants in Huelva, housing standards, a housing alternative for seasonal migrant farm workers	

Annex 2 – Needs Register Terminology

Category of Hazard:

This is the generic description of a hazard, e.g. 'Tractor', Livestock, Chemicals etc. You should list the types of hazards that are relevant to your CoP. Example: Livestock incidents.

Critical Issue(s):

Refers to a specific topic, problem, or concern that poses a risk to the safety and well-being of individuals on the farm and that needs to be addressed to prevent accidents or incidents. There may be a number of 'issues' associated with a single hazard. *Example:* (Livestock incidents) Unsafe animal handling AND calving.

Critical Challenge:

Identification of problems or difficulties that must be addressed to achieve the goal of improving the critical issue. *Example:* Farmers do not have necessary animal handling facilities.

Critical Needs:

The essential requirements, measures, or resources necessary to address safety concerns effectively and ensure a safe working environment on the farm. This identifies the needs of different groups of stakeholders. The stakeholders are classified in line with the Farmer/Citizen, Public organisations, Research and education and Private organisations.

Vulnerable / target populations:

This is the population/people who are at risk of experiencing an injury i.e. farmers, workers, bystanders / others. E.g. whilst all farmers are at risk of 'livestock' related hazards, elderly farmers in Ireland are highly vulnerable. Gender specific vulnerability is that, if women or men are particularly at risk, this is indicated.

Annex 3 – Survey Text

1. In your opinion, what are the highest priorities for making a farm safer?

(Rank the following options, with 1 as the highest priority, 2 as the second priority, etc.)

- Awareness of health and safety risks in farming
- Support to farm safely from family, friends, and important others
- Personal protection use (Hi-vis jackets, eyewear, helmets, etc.)
- Training or support from advisors / farming organisations
- Help on the farm or time to get everything done
- Safe machinery or equipment
- Money to upgrade buildings / farmyard / machinery
- Other _____

2. How would you prefer to learn about farm safety?

(Rank the following options, with 1 as your first preference, 2 as your second preference, etc.)

- In a training course/classroom
- Talking with other farmers and specialists such as in a discussion group
- One-to-one support from an advisor / specialist, e.g. vet or contractor
- Reading about it in the agri-media / on social media
- Talking with family and friends
- Learning on the job or through experience
- Through an easy-to-use risk assessment tool, e.g. booklet or online app
- Other _____

3. Demographics

(Please tick or write in the following information)

Age:

15 – 24 _____

25 – 34 _____

35 – 44 _____

45 – 54 _____

55 – 64 _____

65+ _____

Gender:

Female _____

Male _____

Other _____

Occupation:

Farm manager / owner/ operator _____

Farm worker / employee _____

Farm family member _____

Agricultural Student _____

Farm enterprise that you allocate most of your labour or the farm's labour:

1. Field Crops (E.g. Cereals, Rice, Root crops) _____
2. Horticulture(e.g. Vegetables, Mushrooms) _____
3. Permanent Crops (e.g. Fruit, Vinyards, Olives) _____
4. Grazing Livestock (e.g. Dairying, Beef Cattle, Goats) _____
5. Granivores (e.g. Pigs, Poultry) _____
6. Mixed Cropping (a combination of 1, 2, or 3) _____
7. Mixed Livestock Holdings (a combination of 4 or 5) _____
8. Mixed Crops-Livestock (any combination of 1 - 5) _____
9. Other _____

Total area farmed (hectares worked / owned / rented):

Survey location (where are you filling out this survey?):

1. Training course / Lecture _____
2. Demonstration event (discussion group / farm walk) _____
3. Agricultural event (Fair / conference) _____

Annex 4 – Task 3.4 Guidance Document

Task 3.4 Overview

Task 3.4: Co-designing approaches to increase engagement of specific agricultural production sectors and populations with risk management tools

Leader: TEAGASC. Supporting partners: LUKE; EULS; ZRC SAZU; Oxfam; SVLFG; BEC; IDELE; VDU; Savonia; LBU; UAK.

The objective of this task is to collaborate with CoPs that identify farmer, farm worker, and student engagement with risk management process, i.e. how interventions can be implemented or operationalised by end users. The results of the survey will be used to produce a Technical Note and Practice Abstract. The results will also inform the work of Tasks 3.5 and 3.6 which will co-design, develop and test methods that meet the needs of farmers, farm workers, and students.

This task has two parts, a Survey and a CoP evaluation.

Part 1 Overview: Survey

Teagasc has designed a short survey to identify methods of improving farmer, farm worker, and student engagement with risk management processes across CoP's.

Survey Questions

This survey will be collected by 11 COP administrators and consists of three questions designed to identify optimum implementation strategies. The first two questions are informed by Theories of the Stages of Change, Hierarchy of Controls, and Diffusion of Innovation. The third question collects demographic information to allow cross-sectional analysis of key populations.

1. In Q1, participants rank farm safety/risk management priorities from a list of seven options. There is also an 'other' option. A rank of 1 is the highest priority, 2 is the second priority, etc.
2. In Q2, participants rank their preferred methods of engagement with risk management and farm safety information from a list of seven options and an 'other' fill-in. A rank of 1 is the highest priority, 2 is the second priority, etc.
3. In Q3, Demographic consist of age, gender, farm enterprise, and land area farmed.

What is the aim of the survey?

Collecting data on these three questions will establish a multi-national empirical evidence base with data on farmer, worker, and student priorities for controlling risk and preferences for engagement methods.

Demographic data will allow for cross-sectional analysis identifying the specific preferences of certain groups (e.g. older farmers) and specific enterprises (e.g. dairy farmers) within and across countries.

Part 2 Overview: CoP Evaluation

CoP administrators will enter survey results of this survey into an excel sheet provided by Teagasc to conduct an initial analysis. This empirical evidence base will be evaluated by individual country's COPs.

COP administrators will use the results of their survey as the start of for discussion with COP participants to assess their implications for engaging farmers and students (and other relevant populations) with risk-management systems. As part of this discussion, COPs will be asked to identify additional approaches to engaging end users.

CoP administrators will combine the survey results of Part 1 and the CoP analysis of Part 2 together in an EIP Practice Abstract / Technical Note which will be included in the SHKH and EIP AGRI (Deliverable 1.6). The deadline for this Practice Abstract / Technical Note is June 2025. The data collected by partners, through the survey and the feedback from the CoPs, will support **academic publications**.

I am here to support you throughout this entire process!

Please reach out to me at joseph.firnhaber@teagasc.ie

3.4 Work Plan

This work plan serves as a timeline for completing PA 10.

Please contact me with any questions – I am here to support you!

1. Teagasc Support From start to finish All
2. PA Clinic February Mo.26
3. Guidance for Part 1 February Mo.26
4. Survey Translation February – March Mo.26-27
5. Survey Data Collection February – June Mo.26-29
6. Guidance for Part 2 and PA Template April 30 Mo.28
- 7. Initial 50 Results returned to Teagasc* May 16, 23, 30 - Mo.29**
8. CoP Evaluation Meeting May – June Mo.29-30
- 9. TN Draft 1 June 30 Mo.30**
10. TN Review July Mo.31
11. TN Draft 2 and Draft PA (final) July/August Mo.31-32
12. PA Finalised July/August Mo.31-32
13. TN and PA Submission September Mo.33

*** Data collection extended to May 23 for partners using online surveys, and to 30 for exclusively physical surveys.**

Survey Translation

February – March, Month 26 - 27

1. CoP admins translate the survey text into the local language with Teagasc support.
2. These translations should preserve the meaning of the questions rather than trying to translate literally the questions and responses ‘word-for-word’.
 - a. E.g. Safety systems and engagement options may have specific local equivalents.
 - i. For example, Q 2.3 identifies one-to-one support from an agricultural advisor or other specialist, like a vet. In Ireland, we have professional farm advisors who work with individual farmers and groups of farmers to share best practices across a wide range of farming practices. If your country does not have an equivalent for agricultural advisors, you could reword this question to be exclusively about one-to-one advice from specialists, and list several of the most relevant specialists for farmers in your country.
3. CoP Admins should contact Joe (joseph.firnhaber@teagasc.ie) about any translation questions like these, and we will collaborate on the solution.
4. CoP admins will finalise any large linguistic changes with Joe.
5. CoP admins should document this translation process for the Technical Note Method Section. To use the same example as above, a country which does not commonly use advisors might write something like the following:
 - a. *During translation, we adapted [number] sections of the English survey text to better fit farming contexts in [country]. As agricultural advisors are not commonplace in [country], we changed this question to read: ‘One-to-one support from a specialist, e.g. vet or contractor’*

- b. List each of your meaningful changes out using a format similar to this example.

Survey Data Collection

February to May - Month 26 - 29

1. After translation, CoP admins will collect data until they reach a minimum of **50** completed surveys (at least 1 answer per question) in their country. If you collect more than 50 surveys, this is a bonus.
2. The survey's target population is **adults, i.e. those over 18 years of age**, who contribute to farm work or are likely do so in the future, i.e. agricultural students. **These may include** farmers, farm workers, and agricultural students. The goal of this intentionally wide sampling is to make it as easy and convenient as possible for CoP admins to target several groups most accessible to them.

Populations included in sample

- Farm Owners / Operators / Managers of any farm type
- Farm Employees that contribute to farm work
 - (e.g. permanent, full or part-time, migrant, or seasonal workers)
- Farm Family Members who contribute to farm work
 - (e.g. farm spouses or adult children)
- Agricultural Students studying to contribute to farm work
 - (students must be adults to participate +18)

Populations not included

- Advisors and specialists who work to support farmers
 - E.g. Agricultural advisors, Builders/Construction, Vets, etc.
3. CoP admins will identify the populations or sub-populations that they have the **easiest access** to and begin recruiting from these groups. To do so, admins will print out copies of the surveys and consent forms and hand out these either directly to targeted communities (e.g. at lectures in an agricultural college) and/or at events attended by these groups (e.g. at agricultural fairs).
 - a. Admins do not have to target every group.
 - b. Admins do not have to ensure that their sample is representative or purposefully diverse.
 - c. E.g. Teagasc is distributing surveys through agricultural college classes, general and young-farmer discussion groups, and tabling at farming events. This should give us a mix of Agricultural Students (colleges), Owners and Employees of various ages and farm types (discussion groups) and a wide mix of those working on farms (farming events).

Sampling Methods

4. Distribution methods:
 - a. In-person surveys distributed to individuals or groups at meetings, events, classes, lectures etc.
 - b. Surveys distributed by mail
5. Online Distribution
 - a. Online data collection is done through EU survey (this ensures compliance with GDPR rules). Include consent materials similar to the examples provided in Annex 2 below as part of the introduction to the survey. Then, include your translated question text.
 - b. In our experience at Teagasc, online surveys require clear communication and dissemination activities to ensure that they are successful and reach your target populations. Plan how to disseminate the online portion of the survey and consider

this as a way that you can expand your data collection past 50 individuals or to groups that would otherwise be hard to reach through in-person data-collection.

Administering the Survey

6. Administering the survey is straightforward; instructions are included in both the information sheet and as part of the survey itself. You will find additional information below that will help you to answer participant questions about the survey. Please contact me if you would like additional information!
 - a. When approaching or calling participants, make sure they know that their participation is voluntary. They must agree ('consent') to take part.
 - b. Encourage participants to complete the survey (rank all items) so that our data can be as rich as possible, but if they only rank the top 3, for example, that is ok too.
7. On the survey demographics, there is a space where participants can indicate the location where they are completing this survey.

Survey Analysis and Data Entry

May 16 – (Month 29)

1. Analysis of this data will consist of basic frequency analyses of the two main questions, following two protocols depending on if CoP Admins used online data collection or exclusively in-person. In both cases, the end product for use in analysis will be an Excel Spreadsheet provided by Teagasc. The following protocols are designed to ensure that all Partners and Teagasc have access to finished excel sheets.

For Partners who collected all data in-person

2. CoP admins will input the data from each participant's survey into the Excel sheet provided by Teagasc. The first page of this sheet shows results, which will be automatically generated, and no text needs to be entered. The Excel sheet explains exactly how to enter the data.
 - a. Partners input the 50+ surveys' data into the Excel spreadsheet.
 - b. The Excel spreadsheet will calculate main findings on the first page
 - c. Examine demographics as well to contextualise these findings
 - d. Partners prepare a short presentation for the CoP Evaluation meeting.
 - e. **Before May 30**, Partners send Joe their finalised Excel data sheet with 50+ survey data input and automatically calculated

For partners who collected data using the online surveys

- a. First, CoP partners input data from in-person collection (if any) into the online survey, using the existing survey link – all data is now in one document.
- b. In the final survey box, which describes 'farm size' enter the farm hectares, then a separation (e.g. ____) and then enter the location that your in-person survey was collected. **Write both the farm size and the location data in the same text box.**
- c. Then, Partners notify Joe that your data entry is complete **by May 23 – ideally sooner.**
 - a. This earlier deadline is necessary to allow time for Joe to input all of the online data for multiple partners.
- d. Joe will then enter all of Partners' online data into an excel sheet and send this back to partners.
- e. Partners identify the main findings and examine demographics to contextualise these findings
- f. Partners prepare a presentation for the CoP Evaluation meeting.

CoP Evaluation Meeting

May to June – (Month 29 – 30)

1. The Deliverable requires a report on how each country's survey results can be used to improve this country's safety system. Each country will hold a CoP Evaluation Meeting, to contextualise survey results and identify steps for implementation.

CoP Evaluation Aim

2. The outline below describes the information that CoP admins will report when writing TN 10 from this Evaluation Meeting. **The full TN outline can be found on page 13-14.** This part of the outline is your Reporting Template for the Evaluation meeting, and the outline of topics to discuss.

Technical Note Outline for Pt. 2

1. Evaluation
 - a. Summary of CoP meeting
 - b. Do these results match your CoP's experience
 - c. Do these reported needs of farmers/students match the current approach in your country?
 - d. What do these results miss/what are the limits
 - i. other important groups with specific needs
 - ii. other methods of engagement
 - iii. other safety priorities
2. Implementation
 - a. CoP recommendations for improvement to Country Safety System e.g.:
 - i. Safety infrastructure (tools, buildings, etc.)
 - ii. Education, Agricultural colleges, knowledge sharing
 - iii. Guidance, policy
 - iv. Health system, social security
 - b. Example 'next step' for implementing these improvements or changes.
3. Conclusion
 - a. Synthesis of important findings based on Survey (end user) and CoP (stakeholder) feedback.
3. The most important outcome and the goal of this meeting is 2.a and 2.b. The specific recommendations for improvements (2.a) will vary considerably between Partners, depending on both the country's safety system (including the actor map) and on the survey results. The examples provided (2.a.i-iv.) are not mandatory to cover but are starting points for exploring different avenues for implementing suggested changes. It is also important that the TN not only to identify the desired change in your country's safety system (2.a), but also to describe a meaningful next step towards implementing this change (2.b). Consider the following as an example for how to include both of these:
 - a. Your findings illustrate a strong preference for learning about safety in a classroom or through training. Discussing this with your CoP, you identify that there are many courses already conducted by your organisation. This indicates that the gap could be end-users' engagement with these, their access to or awareness of them, or their interest. Then you can report (2.a) recommendations to improve access to and engagement with these existing resources, such as (2.b) targeting these courses to populations you want to reach or change where they are held to local meeting halls or hotels to make access easier.

Meeting Structure and Recommendations

3. Because of the diversity of results across Partners, you have flexibility with how you structure the CoP meeting as long as you are able to report the appropriate information, and it follows the basic structure:
 - a. Overview of survey findings
 - b. Evaluation discussion
 - c. Implementation discussion

4. You can structure this meeting like your regular CoP meetings, if this is easiest. We recommend allowing for at least an hour of time, beginning with an overview presentation on the survey results, and then using the TN outline as your meeting agenda to go through the Evaluation and Implementation questions. Before you hold the meeting, tailor the Implementation prompts in the TN outline to ones which match your findings, expertise in your CoP, or country's safety system. You can reach out to Teagasc at any point for additional guidance on structuring this meeting.

Work Plan

1. Prepare for the meeting by reviewing the TN outline/reporting template and your data to identify the most relevant results and implementation questions.
2. Ensure you have a way to capture the data you need to report
 - a. Host the meeting online and use a notetaker or review the transcript.
 - b. Have a colleague take notes at an in-person event.
 - c. Break CoP members into groups to write short summaries on paper/sticky-notes and provide their answers.
3. Hold the Evaluation meeting.
4. Report the results in your TN
5. Submit your TN draft to Joe by **June 30**.

Technical Note Process

Complete draft due June 30

1. The Table Below describes the Technical Note and Practice Abstract production process.
 - a. The Technical Note is the longer version of your report on this task.
 - b. The Practice Abstract is the short version (less than 250 words) that you will complete after this.

Step	Description	Who?
Step 1	Guidelines document produced.	Diana/Joe
Step 2	Meeting (Clinic) to present guidance document	Tiina, Diana, Joe
Step 3	Partner submits drafts for review to Diana/Joe	CoP Partners
Step 4	Review & proofread of document to ensure clarity and compliance of guidelines (use "Track changes" when commenting). Suggest key words.	Diana/Joe
Step 5	CoP Partner edits the document and once completed send it back to Diana/Joe.	CoP Partners
Step 6	Diana/Joe have a final check and add comments for layout.	Diana/Joe
Step 7	AEIDL finalizes the layout and provides support with graphic design in order to ensure consistency in the use of templates and the SafeHabitus visual identity.	Anamarija
Step 8	When all edits are completed, the document is finalized, saved as a PDF and Word and sent to CoP partners for approval.	Anamarija
Step 8.1	Partners produce PA summary in English and send to Diana/Joe for review and proofreading. Then, partners produce translation of finalised English version in native language.	CoP Partners
Step 9	Approval of the final version of the Technical Note and Practice Abstract, authors and key words.	CoP Partners

Step 10	AEIDL publish Technical Notes on the SHKH AEIDL generate hyperlinks to Technical Notes in the SHKH and include these in the PAs. Practice Abstract submitted to EU CAP Network and EU FarmBook.	Anamarija
Step 11	Completing and submission of Deliverable 1.6.	David, Leo

Technical Note 10 Full Template

- Title
- Authors and Institution
- Introduction
 - Farm Safety situation in Country (you can link to your Needs Register results)
 - High-level summary of current safety system (primary resources to promote farm safety in Country, you can link to your Actor Map results)
 - Importance of ensuring the current system can accommodate end-users in the specific groups you sampled (e.g. describe why it is important to meet farmworkers/students/etc. specific needs and what those might be – base this section on the primary groups you sampled)
- Survey Methodology
 - Locations and methods of data collection
 - Meaningful translation choices or process (instances where the original survey text had to be altered more dramatically to fit local country contexts)
 - Participant Demographics (Question 3 results – a table is fine here)
- Survey Results
 - Question 1 results (results of frequency analyses of rank-ordered questions)
 - Question 2 results (results of frequency analyses of rank-ordered questions)
- Evaluation
 - Summary of CoP meeting
 - Do these results match your CoP's experience
 - Do these reported needs of farmers/students match the current approach in your country?
 - What do these results miss/what are the limits
 - other important groups with specific needs
 - other methods of engagement
 - other safety priorities
- Implementation
 - CoP recommendations for improvement to Country Safety System e.g.:
 - Safety infrastructure (tools, buildings, etc.)
 - Education, Agricultural colleges, knowledge sharing
 - Guidance, policy
 - Health system, social security
 - Example 'next step' for implementing these improvements.
- Conclusion
 - Synthesis of important findings based on Survey (end user) and CoP (stakeholder) feedback

Consent Form

Farm Safety and Support Priorities Survey

You are invited to take part in a SafeHabitus study on farm safety

Study Information

Farm safety is a critical issue for farmers and their families. In order to improve safety on farms, we need a better understanding of farmer's needs. This survey is part of the SafeHabitus project, which seeks to improve farm safety across Europe. By completing this survey, you will help us accomplish three goals:

1. Identify priority safety issues that farmers face
2. Identify what types of support farmers need
3. Inform improved national and EU policy that supports farmers' health, safety, and security.

This will take about 5 minutes to complete.

The survey consists of three questions. Questions one and two focus on farm safety and question three focuses on personal information.

Participation in this survey is voluntary.

Even if you have agreed to participate, you may withdraw at any time while completing this survey without any repercussion. You cannot withdraw after completing the survey, as your data is fully anonymous and therefore impossible to identify from the larger sample.

Your participation is confidential, and your anonymity is guaranteed, as no identifying information is collected. Information collected through the survey will be used only for the purpose of research leading to publication of reports and academic papers. All data collected through this survey will be securely stored for ten years after the duration of the project to allow for scientific publication and communication at press, policy, and academic outlets. Then, all information collected through this survey will be deleted on or before 31 December 2028. Individual surveys will not be accessed by or shared with anyone outside the project team: David Meredith, Diana van Doorn, John McNamara, and Joseph Firnhaber.

Information concerning personal data

It should be noted that personal data will only be used for the purpose of the study, will be stored securely by Teagasc and not shared outside of the organisation or only shared outside the organisation as specified. Only the minimum amount of personal data necessary will be collected, and it will be stored for the minimum period of time required. The Teagasc Data Protection Officer may be contacted at DPO@Teagasc.ie at any stage. A copy of Teagasc's privacy policy is available at <https://www.teagasc.ie/media/website/publications/2018/Data-Privacy-Notice-A5-4pp.pdf> which provides further information about how Teagasc will process your personal data in connection with the study.

The fully anonymized survey results, including the dataset, will be published on the SafeHabitus website Knowledge Hub, in addition to an open data depository.

There are no anticipated risks for taking part in this research. However, if you have any questions or concerns regarding this survey, please contact Dr. Joseph Firnhaber at 0838712648 or joseph.firnhaber@teagasc.ie

Ethical approval has been attained by the Teagasc Social Science Ethics Committee.

Please read the following statements and sign below if you agree to participate in the study:

1. I consent voluntarily to being a participant in this study.
2. I understand that even if I agree to participate now, I can withdraw without having to give a reason by contacting Dr. David Meredith at David.Meredith@teagasc.ie.
3. I have been given sufficient information about this study and have read and understood this information.
4. I understand that all information I provide in this study will be treated confidentially.

5. I consent to the use of the data in this study to be used in research and in the further development of the SafeHabitus project's efforts towards farm safety.
6. I understand that personal information collected about me that can identify me will not be shared beyond the study team.
7. I understand the project my data is being used for may generate results or outputs that could be commercialised; however, my personal data will not be commercialised in any way without my explicit permission.
8. I give permission for the anonymised data I provide to be deposited in an open data repository so it can be shared and used for learning and potentially reused for future research.

Participant signature

Participant name (BLOCK capitals)

Date:

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